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Announcement Special Issue of 'University News'

A **Special Number of the University News** on the theme '*Higher Education@2047*' is being brought out in the Month of April, 2024.

The **Special Issue** will cover the articles of eminent educationists on the afore-mentioned theme. Readers of the University News are also invited to contribute to the Special Number by submitting papers/articles on the above theme by **April 01, 2024**. The papers will be published in the Issue subject to the approval of the Editorial Committee of the University News. The contributions are invited on the following Subthemes:

Digital Transformation in Higher Education

- The Future of Credentialling: Digital badges, Micro-credentialing and Online Degree
- AI and Analytics in Higher Education: Transforming Decision Making
- Faculty Development and Digital Pedagogies: Empowering Educators

Integrating Bhartiya Knowledge System (BKS) with Higher Education

- Using Bhartiya Knowledge System-based Approach for Teaching-learning for Holistic Development.
- Bhartiya Knowledge System in Sustainable Development.
- Embedding Bhartiya Knowledge System for Futuristic Education.
- Ancient Bharatiya Wisdom in Modern Context: Everlasting Relevance of Indian Knowledge System Heritage for Human Development.
- Return of the Vishwa Guru Status: Strategies to Maintain and Propagate Ancient Indian Wisdom for Global Welfare.
- Embedding Indian Traditional Knowledge into Advanced Scientific Research and Futuristic Technology to Optimise the Advantages.
- Traditional Tribal Knowledge Treasure in India: How to Make Best Use of.
- Challenges in Communication and Dissemination of Traditional Knowledge.

Future of Work and Skill Development

- Sustainable Careers: Navigating a Dynamic Workplace.
- Human-centered Skills in a Tech-driven World: Soft Skills and Emotional Intelligence.
- Resilience & Adaptability: Impact of Gig Economy on Higher Education.

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- Collaborative Research Networks: Fostering Interdisciplinary Research.
- Entrepreneurship and Innovation: From Idea to Impact.
- Innovative Funding Models for Research.

Globalization and Internationalization of Higher Education

- International Collaborations and Partnerships: Building Bridges for Higher Education.
- Global Higher Education Policy and Regulation: Harmonizing Standards.
- Student Mobility and Diversity: Enhancing International Experience.

Any Other Relevant Subthemes

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Teacher Empowerment: Need of the Hour

Amita Pandey Bhardwaj*

We all know that teachers are the backbone of the education system, the heart of the teaching-learning process, and the true implementer of curriculum and educational policies. They play a pivotal role in imparting education and shaping the lives of the students. They also inculcate knowledge, values, and ethics in students' lives and prepare them for further education. Consequently, the role of teachers cannot be overlooked as they contribute immensely to ensure the learning of students which is the sole objective of teaching. Besides this, to address the challenges of the fast-changing educational scenario, teachers must be empowered with the right knowledge, attitude, skills, and competencies in a continuous way. The importance of being empowered is reflected in the fact that how much teachers are capable, sensitive, motivated, enthusiastic, creative, determined, and energized in performing their educational work. As teachers truly shape the future of students thereby future of education, therefore, teacher empowerment is very essential to achieving the goal of real education, linking education with life, and making education meaningful. Against this backdrop, the present article attempts to clarify the conceptual meaning and process of teacher empowerment along with the needed areas of interventions for empowering teachers.

Teacher Empowerment: Conceptual Meaning & Process

Teacher empowerment is a relative term and consists of two words — 'Teacher' and 'Empowerment'. 'Teacher' means a person having teaching skills and possesses certain professional qualities of teaching while 'Empowerment' refers to some criteria. The empowered teachers have the knowledge, skills, and values which help them to act in a given situation and bring improvement in it. Needless to mention, that Knowledge is a means of teacher empowerment rather than of gaining power. Hammond (1997) has rightly said that— "*empowerment must occur through knowledge rather than through new controls that would enfranchise teachers at the cost of others, especially parents who have a deep interest in children's success.*" It is considered as a development of skills which make teachers more confident, and self-reliant and development of abilities which help to make self-decision. The values help the empowered teachers to gain the opportunity in decision-making.

According to Bolin, "Teacher-empowerment means investing teachers with the right to participate in the determination of institutional goals and policies and to exercise professional

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judgment about what and how to teach.” Thus, teacher empowerment is a process of developing competencies that help them take charge of their own professional growth and find solutions to their own problems. In the process of empowerment, the teachers are made to develop the belief that they have the required skills and knowledge to improve their working situations. The dictionary defines empowerment as “to give power or authority to, especially by legal means” and “to enable or permit”. The first meaning emphasises power which is the ability or right to control people or things. It implies that people with power have the authority to influence the actions of others. In other words, empowered people can have power and powerful people can be empowered. Thus, it is possible to be empowered without being powerful and vice versa. In education, some teachers have power while others are powerless which opposes the process of empowerment. The empowered teachers must be given freedom to exercise their own professional judgment without being restricted by others. It is also important to mention that factors like variability, innovation, and creativity which are central to the concept of empowerment and can be propagated only when the teachers are given freedom to work in their own way. The second definition as mentioned above is much closer to express the meaning of an empowered teacher. In this view, being an empowered teacher means having access to information and materials and being free to use these resources in a way that meets student needs and targets. Thus, being an empowered teacher means having enough resources and freedom which he/she can provide to their students with the education that they deserve. Therefore, teacher empowerment is perceived as a crucial factor that affects any institutional effectiveness. The teacher is empowered to the extent to which the path is favourable for his or her development of basic skills, understanding, work habits, desirable attitudes, value judgement and adequate adjustment with their students. Apart from teaching and maintaining a relationship, an empowered teacher also engages in community work, attend conferences, do professional reading, and a member of a professional organisation. An empowered teacher is also time-conscious which means accomplishing all the duties and responsibilities on time, especially when it comes to submitting of assigned work, question papers,

report grades, etc. Thus, empowerment is a process where the teachers develop the competence to take charge of their own growth. The process of empowerment involves three steps viz. Clarity, Support, and Autonomy are described below:

Step-1: Clarity

The first step in the process of empowerment is to clarify goals and expectations. The teachers can only progress at work if they know about the answers to two queries viz. what the objective is ? and what results they are expected to deliver? With empowerment the role of a teacher shifts from closely supervising to what students are doing to make them accountable for results. This means that teachers need to clearly define the expected outcomes and communicate to students so that everyone understands their responsibilities.

Step-2: Support

The second step of empowering the teachers is to support them by providing the needed resources to succeed and removing barriers, if any, that may hinder progress. The teachers empower their students by catering to their needs. This requires not only providing the time, resources, and encouragement necessary for accomplishing goals but also actively working to eliminate barriers to ensure success.

Step-3: Autonomy

The third step of empowering teachers is providing them with the autonomy they need to carry out their academic work. Autonomy is the degree of freedom and discretion that teachers have over their work tasks, goals, and methods. It leads to accountability which means the extent to which they are responsible for the outcomes and consequences of their work. Once the teachers know what they are expected to do and have the support they need to do it then the best thing a teacher can do is to get out of their way.

Thus, intelligent use of these three steps in the form of Clarity, Support, and Autonomy will help in empowering the teachers successfully.

Needed Interventions for Teacher Empowerment

The areas of interventions needed for teacher empowerment can be Professional Development, Action Research, skill upgradation, Learner centric pedagogical procedures, and Nurturing Human

Values, and Digital Skills which are briefly discussed here.

Empowerment through Professional Development

As teaching is a profession, we can say that a professionally developed teacher is a professionally empowered teacher. The professional preparedness, competence, dedication & willingness of the teacher is directly linked with quality education. It is the quality of the teacher which is the key determinant of quality education. It has been aptly expressed by the university education commission (1948-49) that “People in this country have been slow to recognize that education is a profession for which intensive preparation is necessary as it is in any other profession.” This is alive in its relevance even today as we know that teaching is a profession and Teacher education is a process of professional preparation of teachers. Preparing one for a profession is an arduous task & it involves action from multiple fronts & perspectives. The professional development of the teacher is mainly concerned with the competence, commitment & values associated with his/her teaching, learning assessment, and research work. Consequently, raising the levels of competence & commitment of teachers will help them in becoming a true professional. Thus, teacher empowerment is most effective when it focuses on teacher professionalism.

Empowerment through Action Research

This is very powerful and potent research for empowering teachers at the levels of *will and skill* which leads to the enhancement of commitment & competence levels respectively. It is carried out as a small invention by the practitioner to advance the solution of the concrete problems arising from their real educational situation through the application of the scientific method. Its flexibility, dynamism, and situation-specific character have a direct address to those teachers who are keen to improve their cognitive abilities and competencies to become professionally able, capable, and committed. The regular practice of this type of research not only improves the educational practices but also the professional competencies of the practitioner. Teachers of all disciplines and levels of education must be sensitised & trained in using this research so that it becomes easier for them to make it as an integral part of their educational practices. Besides this capacity building through Action Research based programmes can be

designed & developed by the training centres for teachers and head of the institution for their faculty members. Thus, Action Research has tremendous potential for empowering the teachers in the 21st century educational scenario.

Empowerment through Skill Upgradation

Skill development, skill upgradation & skill enrichment are the focus of education system which have been advocated by NEP 2020 also. These skills are associated with planning, designing, implementing & evaluating any educational process, programme, material & system. Besides content knowledge, teachers must possess discipline specific cognitive skills, pedagogical skills and assessment skills. These skills will empower the teachers not only to carry out their day-to-day academic work but also in handling their teaching learning processes in a more meaningful, efficient & effective way.

Empowerment through Learner-Centric Pedagogic Procedures

The learner centric pedagogy is the prime focus of transactional strategies especially of the teaching-learning process for ensuring better learning outcomes. There are number of learner centric procedures viz. reflective teaching, adaptive teaching, cooperative teaching, e-learning, experiential learning, art & sport integrated learning, concept mapping, brainstorming, etc. The teachers should be given insight and training in the process of using these pedagogic procedures in a way that enable them to practice in their classroom. The effective use of all these procedures requires reflection-for-action, reflection-in-action & reflection-on-action by the practitioners.

Empowerment through Nurturing Human Values

The nurturing of human values such as compassion, fellow feeling, kind, sympathy, empathy, etc will ensure the ability to transcend parochial feelings related to caste, colour, creed, and religion. These values will promote the feeling of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam* which has been advocated in one of the pillars of education viz. Learning to live together in Delor’s report- ‘Learning the Treasure Within’. In addition to this, the National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (2009) envisions Preparing Professionals and Humane Teachers. The nurturing of these human values will empower teachers as humane teachers thereby ensuring that teachers will

work with integrity, dedication, and commitment along with an empathetic attitude toward their students and colleagues.

Empowerment through Digital Skills

In the present era of technology, digital skills are of paramount importance in the educational world. These skills are needed not only for the accessing & managing of information anytime from anywhere by anyone but also in designing, developing, presenting, delivering, processing & retrieving information in an easy, efficient & efficient way. They also help to create, communicate, collaborate and share digital content in the form of image, text, audio & video. Needless to mention that empowering teachers with technological skills have great impact on student's achievement. NEP 2020 has also stressed on the extensive use of technology in teaching and learning in its guiding principles. Thus, 21st century teachers must be equipped with digital skills, knowledge and attitudes for ensuring the confident, creative and critical use of technologies in their teaching learning process.

In a nutshell, it can be said that teacher empowerment is the key to quality teacher and quality education. The promotion of knowledge, attitude, skills & competencies have to be given due importance as power to empower teachers thereby enabling them to address the changing needs and challenges of future educational scenario. This must be carried-out through tailor made need-based training programmes in a mission-mode at institutional, state & central levels. Some of the needed interventions hinted and identified in

this paper will provide a blue print for designing the capacity building training programmes for teachers. Thus, HRDCs of UGC and Centres under PMMMNMTT scheme, especially Faculty Development Centres (FDCs) & Teaching Learning Centres (TLCs) at Higher Education level now renamed as Malviya Mission Teacher Training Centres (MMTTCs) while DIETs, SCERTs & NCERT at School level must play a catalytic role in continuous professional development & growth of teachers by designing competency-based workshops. The teachers should be given support, encouragement & incentives to be the part of these training programmes so that they come-up & live-up with the expectations of the education system.

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Does Learning in the Mother Tongue as Medium of Instruction Help?

G Gopalakrishnan*

Ever since the UNESCO Conference of 1999 on promoting the importance of “Cultural and Linguistic Diversity and Multilingualism” there has been quite some activities right across the globe with conferences and working groups of policymakers, researchers, practitioners, and development actors to exchange views, share good practices, and discuss experiences, focusing on “Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education”, and wider interests on language issues towards sustainable development. The *Asia-Pacific Multilingual Education Working Group (MLE WG)* has been sincere in their efforts in organising series of conferences and meetings since 2003 on the promotion of mother tongues and multilingual transformative education and resilient futures.

This paper is a peripheral one touching on the advantages that one could gain by introducing mother tongue as the sole media of instruction in schools at the primary stages up to Grade 5, as indicated in the NEP 2020 (National Education Policy). Interests in this field of introducing the mother tongue as the media of instruction in primary and secondary stages of schooling has been voiced since the beginning of the 2020s all over the Asia Pacific and the African regions; finding it to be a replacement for the English language. On the other hand, as of current usage, the English we had inherited from the British, happens to be tied with all professions and continue to use the language for all practical purposes. English is still being spoken widely across and happens to be a basic qualification to obtain higher positions in the industry, academia and other societal assignments.

About 40% of the global population does not have access to education in the language that they speak. Learners from ethnolinguistic minorities have several factors to resist gaining education due to poverty, language, lack of proper communication, or remoteness of locations. This learning crisis seems to have severely affected those who speak a different language other than what the teaching media offers.

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This happens to be true for a large amount of the population, particularly in African and interior parts of Asia-Pacific and South American regions who continuously need to travel several miles before they could reach “human habitation”! This is multiplied by the lack of digital and internet communications. Hence, a need to have education in the language spoken at home or the mother tongue.

Way back, as early as 1951, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) convened a meeting of experts to discuss the future use of the mother tongue in developing countries. As reported by Fishman, in summarising the report, it was observed that:

- The mother tongue is a person’s natural means of self-expression and one of his first need is to develop his power of self-expression;
- Every pupil should begin his formal education in his mother tongue.
- There is nothing in the structure of any language that precludes it from becoming a vehicle of modern civilization.

Concerns were being raised on the absorption of students from the mother tongue-educated media, in that they may not be suitable for global assignments in countries where English was taught from the primary level. Fortunately, these concerns are not insurmountable, and can be addressed by proper planning and investments, a firm commitment, and of course adequate funding from the local governments. It was in the year 2000, that writers and scholars from all parts of Africa gathered in Asmara, Eritrea, for a conference, “Against All Odds: African Languages and Literatures into the 21st Century”.

In 2019, during the 3rd high-level policy forum on Multilingual Education, at Bangkok, “Statement on Language and Inclusion”, was endorsed by 16 countries in the Asia Pacific region, to address inequalities in languages in education. The proven success of Multilingual Education (MLE) programmes in enhancing learning outcomes for multilingual learners has been overshadowed by resistance and

international pressure to introduce global languages like English earlier in the curriculum, especially in mother-tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE) programmes.

UNESCO had also been organizing a series of conferences and meetings to highlight the global crisis in education - one of “equity and inclusion, quality and relevance” drawing attention to the loss of indigenous languages shortly- a task which could contradict Sustainability Development Goals (SDG 4 – Education). More pessimistic, but also realistic estimates claim that 90-95 percent of ethnic languages will become extinct or seriously endangered by the end of this century”.

Indian Diaspora

India has been at the forefront of education for the past 2000 years – Vedic, Brahmanical, Buddhist, Muslim, British - and has been seen through diverse aspects, due to the various invasions India has been subjected to. British rule in India gave us the English language, which now seems to be the common language, and also the media of instruction, in most of the States of the Indian Union.

English was made the official language of India in the year 1835, during the tenure of William Bentinck (1828-1835) as the Governor-General of India, based on the “Minute on Indian Education” that sought to establish the need to impart English education to Indian *natives*, by Lord Thomas Babington Macaulay.

According to the 2018 Official Census across

India, almost 19500 languages or dialects are being spoken as mother tongues. It has also been indicated that 96.71% of the population of 140.76 Crores (2021) people had at that time one of the 22 scheduled languages as their mother tongue. This had been a major hindrance at arriving at a single unified language as media of instruction, right across the country.

To quote, “*If the English educated neglect, as they have done and even now continue, as some do, to be ignorant of their mother tongue, linguistic starvation will abide - Mahatma Gandhi.*”

From the following Table 1, it could be observed that a large number of the Indian population are first-language speakers. (Some select data are to be verified).

UNESCO General Conference Held in 1999

During the session of the UNESCO Conference in 1999, it was generally discussed that education could be through the mother tongue, as it could facilitate a better understanding of what is taught, right from the primary education level. “Research shows that education in the mother tongue is a key factor for inclusion and quality learning, and it also improves learning outcomes and academic performances. This is crucial, especially in primary schools to avoid knowledge gaps and increase the speed of learning and comprehension. Most importantly, multilingual education based on the mother tongue empowers all learners to fully take part in society. It fosters mutual understanding and respect for one another and helps preserve the

Table 1 Statistics on the Various Indian Languages Spoken by People in India Ethnologue (2023)

S. No.	Speakers	First Language Speakers	Second Language Speakers	Speakers of the Total World
1	English	380 Billion	1,077 Billion	1,456 Billion
2	Hindi	528,347,19	266 Million	609 Million
3	Bengali	274 Million	39 Million	273 Million
4	Urdu	71 Million	161 Million	232 Million
5	Marathi	83 Million	16 Million	99 Million
6	Telugu	83 Million	13 Million	96 Million
7	Tamil	79 Million	8 Million	87 Million
8	Gujarati	57 Million	5 Million	62 Million
9	Kannada	44 Million	15 Million	9 Million
10	Bhojpuri	2 Million	0.2 Million	2 Million
11	Eastern Punjabi	48 Million	4 Million	52 Million

wealth of cultural and traditional heritage that is embedded in every language around the world. Globally, progress is being made in multilingual education based on mother tongue with the growing understanding of its importance, particularly in early schooling, and more commitment to its development in public life” -- UNESCO’s General Conference in 1999.

National Education Policy -2020

After a gap of several decades, our government introduced the (NEP 2020) National Education Policy 2020. This is perhaps the first large-scale attempt to reform our educational system since 1986. “Multilingualism and the power of language” highlights the importance of the mother tongue as the media of education that is to be adopted, wherever possible, until Grade 5, preferably up to Grade 8 and beyond! The logic behind this concept is that young children could learn and grasp simpler and more difficult concepts quickly if initiated in their mother tongue or home language. The NEP 2020 considers English only as an international language which everyone should learn for convenience in life, not the basis of intelligence. Even a person who knows only a regional or national language can also be intelligent. National Education Policy 2020 was approved by the Union Cabinet on 29th July 2020.

In summary, NEP 2020 or National Education Policy 2020 outlines the framework for the elementary education system, besides vocational training across the country. The NEP 2020 replaces the National Policy on Education of 1986 and spells out a significant shift affecting certain specific changes.

“At the heart of National Education Policy 2020 lies the objective to realize an innovative, student-centric structure that segments student education into four stages: Foundational, Preparatory, Middle, and Secondary. The stages are considered crucial and in a natural order where students progress from one stage to another mentally, shaping and broadening the thought process holistically.”

The most important amongst them is the transition from a 10 + 2 structure to a 5 + 3 + 3 + 4 system”. {Foundational Phase – 5 years – Ages 3 to 8; Pre-school (Grades 1st & 2nd); Preparatory Phase – 3 years – Ages 8 – 11 (Grades 3rd to 5th); Middle Phase – 3 years – Ages 11 – 14 (Grades 6th to 8th);

Secondary Phase – 4 years – Ages 14 -18 (Grades 9th to 12th)}

Advantages of Learning in the Mother Tongue as a Medium of Instruction

Several advantages do accrue while introducing the media of education in Grades 1-5, as per the (NEP 2020) New Education Policy 2020. Many countries had adopted them long before World War II, Japan, Germany, Italy, and China to name a few. Even research was reported in their languages. Most of the research for the war effort was carried out in their laboratories with their scientists and most of the documentation was in their script and languages.

Children taught in their mother tongue would build a strong home-school partnership, and this could help the parents’ participation in the child’s education more wholesome and increase the interest the parents in the child’s educational progress. The child who learns in the mother tongue is aware of its cultural and family base, has a sort of self-confidence generated within and improves his communication skills while arguing and discussing with his parents and peers. Since there is difficulty in taking education deeper into the villages, there may be a better camaraderie between the primary school teachers and the parent community. Further, primary school teachers would feel more comfortable in teaching the mother tongue, as they may not find a better way to express more freely, rather than translate their English thinking to the children in Grades 1 -5.

Primary education in the mother tongue, with books in the local languages, would bring the children closer to the habit of reading through the textbooks; and make them understand and appreciate the subjects better. Rather than Rote learning through English / foreign media. ‘Mother tongue education’ would bring the children closer to their cultural background, appreciating the past values and their ‘home culture’ better!

A child taught via a language that it cannot understand would result in the child memorizing the study material without a proper understanding and comprehension. ‘Home language or mother tongue’ would perhaps reduce the number of school drop-outs at a young age, due to the child being uncomfortable with an alien language. Psychologically it would now

be able to learn some additional languages through the first language – the mother tongue.

As per UNESCO, 40% of the world's population are taught through media that is not their own, and hence many countries are likely to lose their cultural heritage and their languages as well! It was Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam who said "*Imparting education to children in vernacular languages shall encourage creativity and enable children easy grasp of the subject.*"

Conclusions

Across Africa, and Asia-Pacific regions there have been for long discussions held to consider changing the medium of instruction for children from English to their respective home languages or mother tongue! The *Asia-Pacific Multilingual Education Working Group (MLE WG)* has been ardently supporting this concept, and the participating countries have been seriously working on proposals to change the educational systems accordingly. This was also on the United Nations Agenda 2030 "Call for Good Practices"; the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs Call, spotlights the need to ensure "inclusive and equitable quality education promoting life-long learning for all"-Sustainable Development Goal 4 – SDG 4.

Our government in India has come up with the National Education Policy (NEP2020) replacing the 1986 policy which was in continuance till now. This envisages "*students' progression is from one stage to another mentally, shaping and broadening the thought process holistically*"; which implies that the child starts education from the beginning in its mother tongue or home language.

Advantages arising out of this change are that the children learning through their mother tongue build a strong home-school partnership, are brought closer to the reading habit, improve their self-confidence and communication skills, make them appreciate and understand the subjects which they learn. This could also at the same time reduce the school drop-outs, and enable the children to learn about their past cultural backgrounds.

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The Global Artificial Intelligence Revolution

Ajay Kumar Gupta*

Recently, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its applications have emerged as a rapidly advancing technology, affecting almost all facets of our daily lives. It is on the path of turning into a crucial force in achieving our national goal of building a \$5 trillion economy and becoming the third-largest economy in the world by the year 2025. The varied applications of AI are not just restricted to limited fields; rather, technology is gradually becoming the backbone of all social, industrial, and educational avenues. Many researchers are studying the role of newer technologies in Education and related fields. Discussed the benefits of 5G network connectivity in education. In the role of cloud computing technologies in startups was examined. Similar to these, AI tools and applications are also empowering students, teachers, parents and other associated professionals within the educational infrastructure. In the proposed article, we discuss in brief the concept of AI, along with its applications and popular implementations, which are available and useful in the field of education and learning. AI based chatbots are some of the most popular tools currently available that help provide targeted information to the users. This article will primarily focus on OpenAI's ChatGPT, Google Bard and Microsoft Copilot. The article also covers the supplementary and newly emerging fields like prompt engineering, used in extracting exact and accurate information.

Today, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its applications are emerging as the most popular fields in technology, and their impact is visible in almost every other field as well, with significant social, economic, and pedagogical implications. In the educational backdrop, learners and educators are continuously utilizing technology to enhance the output of the efforts aimed at improving learning and training. The journey that began with the initial integration of basic computer-based educational tools has now reached a point where powerful AI-enabled technology is revolutionizing the field. Our nation is steadily moving forward from being a developing country into a developed one, and we will achieve the goal

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before the presently determined period. Apart from the crucially important human resources, it is clear that to achieve our goal, the integration and optimal use of AI applications and tools are also required. India is a country with teenagers holding a significant fraction of the population, and to get the maximum output from this human resource, the youth should certainly be equipped with the latest technologies. In the current global situation, we cannot ignore the importance of AI and its applications since they are becoming the backbone of major fields like defense, robotics, automation, and education.

Keeping in mind the significance of AI, many multinational and national organizations are providing AI tools, creating a huge database to serve the people, and providing instant information and support. Google holds quite an important position in the lives of most people interacting with technology due to its large number of popular applications that are used for day-to-day tasks globally. Many other companies are also providing several paid and even free and open source resources to assist users in their educational, training, and learning activities.

Further, discussing the concepts and implementation of AI brings into the picture the widely popular AI-based chatbots. AI chatbots have rapidly gained mainstream usage in the daily lives of individuals and organizations. Though Google Search gets the credit of being the pioneer in serving information simply and instantly, one has always needed to put in a lot of effort and time to get the most accurate and relevant information. However, the entire situation was completely disrupted with the advent of ChatGPT from Open AI. It aims to provide the most accurate information to the users, but also to make searching for it easier and as natural as possible with the backing of AI. With its growing popularity, Google and Microsoft also introduced their own AI tools, Bard and Copilot respectively, with upgraded databases and utilities. The importance of the field of prompt engineering has increased with the introduction of more such AI chatbots. We will try to introduce the field here. There's no doubt that AI-empowered tools and applications will revolutionize the entire educational learning and training scenario in the upcoming years,

[3] discussed the role of ChatGPT in e-learning. In the further sections, we will discuss in brief the concept of AI and the importance of AI tools in the educational industry among not only students but also teachers.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The concept of AI came into existence to replicate natural human intelligence. Human intelligence is naturally capable of understanding and solving problems, making ethical decisions, reasoning, and emotional comprehension. Researchers and innovators are trying to develop simulations of human intelligence with the use of technology and computer systems, due to which the concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI) emerged as a new branch of computer science. Realizing the power of AI, almost all business, social, economic, and educational areas are swiftly integrating it in their day-to-day and professional activities. [1], [5] discussed the role of AI in the field of education. Applications of Education are also highlighted in [9].

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a branch of computer science that focuses on creating and managing technology capable to learn and acquire knowledge and autonomously make decisions and actions on behalf of a human being. The field includes various types of software and hardware components that support machine learning, expert systems, generative AI, and many more technologies. Some important features in the field of education that Artificial Intelligence helps in enhancing are given below:

Personalized Learning Environment for Everyone

It simulates a personalized environment with multiple responses to resolve the problems raised by the user. Virtually, its applications will give personal guidance and support.

Bridging Learning Gaps

It provides quality content and support without any learning barrier. The user can get accurate information and support from around the globe while sitting in any corner of the world with just an internet connection. No jurisdiction or language barrier can restrict the problem-solving capability. Everyone from villages to metro cities, from rural to urban areas, gets equal opportunities to obtain responses and support from AI-empowered tools.

Feedback and Assessment Support

AI empowered tools are available for both learners and teachers for providing feedback and assessment, which may be helpful to identify the areas where improvement is required.

Lifelong Upgradation of Skills

Without Any Geographical restriction and age barrier, the users can upgrade their skills and knowledge as per their convenience and availability with the use of AI powered tools. This can lead to a smoother educational experience for everyone.

Access to Infinite Content and Curriculum

AI tools can access the infinite information available on the internet. It can provide an accurate response in a few seconds and can categorize it as per the needs of the user. A human may take hours to get the same response.

Research and Innovation

AI applications are playing a very important role in the field of research and innovation providing all the related information and guidance to researchers and academicians. Various tools of AI are available to assist academicians in different activities such as:

- Patent Filing.
- Research Publication.
- Simulation.
- Project Preparation.
- Collaborative support.
- Innovation activities and so on.

AI in Special Education

For students with learning difficulties, the use of AI in special education has the potential to be revolutionary. For instance, speech recognition software can help students who struggle with language, while AI-powered visual aids can improve comprehension for people who are blind or visually impaired.

AI-powered systems can analyze vast amounts of data on student performance, preferences, and learning styles to create tailored educational content and adaptive learning paths. This personalization allows students to learn at their own pace, focusing more on the areas where more support is required.

It's true that AI-supported tools and programs offer features to improve the training and learning process, but their goal is not to take the role of teachers. On the contrary, AI tools may assist teachers along with the students, who have a major role in directing and encouraging their learning.

Artificial intelligence in education is a revolutionary step towards a more efficient, customized, and inclusive learning environment in India. We can raise the bar for education and provide every student the chance to realize their full potential by utilizing artificial intelligence.

Artificial Intelligence – Chatbots

The ultimate goal of chatbots in the field of Artificial Intelligence is to simulate human-like conversation with the user through textual, visual, or voice interactions. The ELIZA laid the foundation of chatbot technology, which was developed by Joseph Weizenbaum at MIT in around 1994. Later an open-source chatbot, Alice was developed by Richard Wallace in 1995. Alice was capable of using natural language processing, which allowed it to hold much more sophisticated conversations. Later, Jabberwacky and Mitsuku appeared as more chatbot tools for the users.

Objective

The objective of chat tools is to answer queries, resolve tasks, and provide desired information, have voice interactions, and hold natural conversations.

Sources of Information

The sources of information of chatbot tools include their databases, websites and other resources from the internet.

Features

The chatbot applications are active and available round the clock without any jurisdiction barrier with equal opportunities, automated responses, personalized interactions, and regular knowledge upgradation. The users can ask their converse in a natural, human-like language, even for sophisticated queries, and receive responses almost instantly, in the form of various media including text, images, and voice.

Various Chatbot Tools

OpenAI - ChatGPT

ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, revolutionized the field of natural language processing and was

the pioneer in developing a user-facing chat application. It is based on the Generative Pre-trained Transformer architecture, which popularized the concept and power of Artificial Intelligence among the users. This tool was designed to get human-like input to provide accurate responses in text or spoken form. Even now, it is already playing an important role in educational training and learning avenues. [7], [8] discussed the role of ChatGPT in the field of education.

ChatGPT is available in both free and paid versions, with the paid version providing additional features and more powerful language models. The official website of OpenAI's ChatGPT can be accessed using [10]. Some features of ChatGPT are:

- Pre-trained Large Language Model.
- Ability to understand human-like input in the form of text.
- Provides accurate output with ability to regenerate in more formats.
- Ability to manage prompts and responses.
- Ability to store and share responses in the form of documents.

The Figure 1 shows the initial screen of ChatGPT tool, where we enter prompt to get a response.

We give input in the form of a prompt, a text query, to get the desired output from the ChatGPT. Some examples are shown below.

- **Prompt:** create HTML code for the menu
- **Response:** This will produce coding in HTML to create a menu, the same may be tested by creating a HTML file.
- **Prompt:** create code in HTML for converting numbers to words
- **Response:** This will produce coding in HTML to convert a given number into a word, the same may be tested by creating a html file.
- **Prompt:** Please tell me about G20.
- **Response:** This will provide information about G20 in detail.
- **Prompt:** Please write an application for leave

The tool application provides an option to regenerate responses and get different versions of the output for the same prompt.

Figure 1: Initial Screen of ChatGPT

E-mail Automation

The users can use power of AI in e-mail activities such as adding the ChatGPT Writer extension. The users will get the ChatGPT writer icon in their e-mail. In Figure 2, we are directing ChatGPT Writer to create an application for a 3-day leave and in response, a draft for the same has to be generated. We may change contents of the draft as needed.

In the Figure 3, the e-mail draft is inserted into the e-mail composing window and with the necessary changes, the same can be sent to the recipient.

Another useful application of AI in e-mails is to generate reply of a received mail. The ChatGPT writer can be used to read, understand and prepare the draft of reply automatically. The user will get a formatted reply, and after making the necessary modifications and updates, the same may be sent as a response to the mail. The users can draft any kind of mails by simply giving an appropriate prompt to ChatGPT writer, like e-mails for a applying to a position, joining, project discussion and much more.

Figure 2: Response for 3 day application e-mail generation

Google Bard

After the phenomenal success of ChatGPT, Google also introduced its own AI Chatbot tool, Google Bard. It is based on the Pathway Language Model (PaLM) technology. Like ChatGPT, Bard can be used for generating automated responses, translating between languages, creating personalized content and extracting precise information based on the input prompt/query. The users can interact with Google Bard using text and voice prompts, and even other modes. Google Bard generates three separate

responses for the given prompt. The official website of Google Bard can be accessed at [11]. Some key features and benefits offered by Bard are illustrated as [12]:

- **Conversational:** Bard can hold natural, engaging conversations, understanding the context, and respond in a relevant way.
- **Generative:** Bard can generate creative text formats, like poems, code, scripts, musical pieces, etc., based on your prompts or instructions.

Figure 3: Insertion of Response e-mail Windows

Figure 4: Initial Screen of Google Bard

Figure 5: Coding in C for Bubble Sorting

Figure 6: Algorithm for Bubble Sorting

- **Informative:** Bard can access and process vast amount of information to provide comprehensive and informative answers to your questions.
- **Multilingual:** Bard currently supports 46 languages, allowing you to interact with it in your preferred language.

Bard can be a helpful tool for learning, writing, and creative exploration. It can assist you with tasks

like research, translation, and content creation. Bard can also be a fun and engaging conversational partner. Figure 4 shows the initial screen of Bard Application.

Figure 5 shows an example of generating program code in C implementing “bubble sort” in response to the Prompt: “Please write programme in C for Bubble sorting”.

Figure 7: Initial Screen of Microsoft Copilot

Figure 6 illustrates a prompt that gives the standard algorithm for bubble sorting in response to the Prompt: “Please write algorithm for bubble sorting”.

Other Examples are:

- **Prompt:** Explain the plot of the movie Sholay in a rhyme of 8 lines
- **Output:** This will display the story in the form of a poem.
- **Prompt:** Same in Hindi
- **Response:** The poem will be shown in Hindi language.

In conclusion, Bard is also an extremely powerful AI tool, which can be used for limitless purposes to enhance creativity and knowledge.

Microsoft Copilot

Copilot is another AI-powered productivity tool launched by Microsoft. It was earlier known as Bing-Chat. It is based on Large Language Models (LLMs) and designed to work alongside Microsoft Office 365 apps. This is powered by GPT-4 along with the DALL-E 3 model. The official website of Microsoft Copilot can be accessed using [13]. The initial screen of Copilot can be seen in Figure—7.

Microsoft Copilot also includes almost all features of the other chat applications discussed above.

Some key features it provides are given below:

- Personalized Responses.
- Chat-based Interface.
- Enhanced Productivity.
- Enhanced Creativity.
- Integration with Microsoft 365 Apps.

In the same manner, we can submit prompt to extract accurate response. For example, the prompt “Create a program in C to check if the given number is prime or not” will generate the relevant code in the C language. Similarly, a prompt like “Brief information about G20 summit in India” will provide summarized details about the summit.

Prompt Engineering

This term is associated with the AI based chatbot applications. The accuracy of the response from the chatbots highly depends on the clarity of the question raised, which is known as a prompt. It is an emerging field of Artificial Engineering, which plays a pivotal role in obtaining an effective and accurate response from the chatbot tools. Prompt engineering refers to the process of creating and designing prompt to direct the tools appropriately and get an accurate response from the chatbot tools.

The role of a prompt engineer is gradually becoming very important with the use of AI-powered

tools. A prompt engineer having the following skills may contribute in extracting the information in more effective manner:

- Effective communication capability.
- Awareness of programming.
- Awareness of AI technology.
- Data analysis efficiency.
- Understanding of the strengths and limitations of AI tools.
- Awareness about the enabled features.
- Awareness about the free and paid features.

With the invention and mainstream adoption of AI, prompt engineering has emerged as a brand new position needed to leverage the full potential of AI systems. Business organizations are realizing the need for prompt engineers to access accurate information and fully utilize AI systems. To achieve a timely and accurate response from the AI system, the prompt engineer follows the steps mentioned below:

- Identify the task and its objective.
- Design the correct input path for AI tools as a prompt.
- Generate outcome from the prompt.
- Evaluate the output and regenerate if necessary.
- Improve the prompt to enhance the output.
- Documentation of extracted output.
- Effective presentation.

Integration of GPT-4 Model

GPT-4 stands for Generative Pre-trained Transformer 4. It is an improved model from Open AI over the earlier model GPT-3.5. It is a multimodal model, meaning it can handle both text and images as input, in contrast to earlier models that were only able to handle text inputs. The paid version of ChatGPT supports the GPT-4 model. Key features of this model are given below:

- Input and output size increased from 3000 words to 25000 words.
- It has multimodal capabilities, so it can understand text and is also capable of interpreting images.

- Users are even able to create websites by just explaining the design on paper.
- Improved ability to handle logical situations.
- Playing the role of a personal trainer and tutor in a more effective manner.
- Uses deep learning to provide more accurate responses.
- Ability to design simple and advanced games.
- Supporting and suggesting ways to organizations to promote and upgrade their business.

Limitations of AI Chatbots

It is true that with the innovation of GPT-4, users are getting more sensible and natural support from AI applications, but they still cannot replace human intelligence. AI applications are tools for assistance in acquiring knowledge and information, but we often need to verify and check the responses provided. Some limitations of AI tools are given below:

- Depends on pre-trained data.
- No emotions.
- No ethics.
- Lack of creativity.
- Limited understanding of the context.
- Possibility of different responses from different versions e.g. GPT-3.5/ GPT-4, for the same prompt.
- Recurrent knowledge upgradation is required.
- Need expertise in prompt engineering for efficient usage.

Key Differences between ChatGPT, Bard, and Copilot (Bing)

After the huge success and popularity of ChatGPT, Google and Microsoft also introduced their AI models, Bard and Copilot (Bing-Chat) respectively. All these models provide similar AI-powered services to the users but with some differences. Users can choose the service they need by analyzing their limits and availability of features. Some key differences between these models are shown in Table-1.

Table 1: Salient Features of ChatGPT, Bard and Copilot

Particulars	ChatGPT	Bard	Copilot
Developed by	OpenAI	Google	Microsoft (Earlier Bing Chat)
Based on Model	Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (GPT)	Pathway Language Model (PaLM)	GPT-4 and DALL-E 3
Chat/Words/ Characters limit	Upto 25000 words at a time		
Pricing	\$20 per month / Free version also available	Free	Free
Availability	ChatGPT 3.5 is free, ChatGPT 4 is paid	Available for free	Available for free, integrated in Microsoft 365
Multimodality	Does not support image and voice prompts. Generates only text responses.	Supports image and voice prompts. Generates responses across text and images.	Supports voice prompts. Generates responses across text and images
Information accessibility	Nov., 2022	Real time data, continuously syncs data from Google	Real time data, mainly search on the different website/ web-portals

Conclusion

The contents of this article demonstrate the power of AI chatbot tools and their potential applications in fields like education, industries, health, content, communication, etc. The features increase efficiency, data analysis, personalized support, innovation, decision-making, knowledge enhancement, and creativity, encouraging people to use these AI tools in their personal, business, and professional tasks.

AI tools collect and analyze the data of the users to improve their services, and therefore, appropriate

safeguards are required to supplement the use of these applications.

In these contemporary times, it is impossible to ignore the use of AI tools, but it is also important that we do not fully rely on them. These tools should be considered as assistive services only and should be integrated with our human resources and intelligence, which will lead to quick, accurate, and dependable solutions to our problems.

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National Education Policy-2020: Research and Innovations for Transforming Higher Education

Prasenjit Das* and Gouri Das**

Innovation does not mean incorporating modern technologies or discoveries into the curriculum. Instead, it should be designed to foster creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving. It should also include activities facilitating collaboration and communication between students and teachers. The individual may slightly deviate from the traditional instructional strategy, which improves how effectively the idea's significance is communicated (Sarta, 2022). Education that is creative sparks students' curiosity, which may be better for conceptualising (Singh, 2021). The educational study reflects the idea's present popularity on a global scale. The professionals have the abilities required to provide high-quality instruction while involved in the teaching-learning process (Mishra, 2023). Innovation inspires students to use their critical thinking skills to address challenging problems. It is easier to build creative problem-solving abilities when one can innovate in mental processes and look for uniqueness in everything (Chattopadhyay, 2020). The essential factor in deciding whether students learn anything that counts in the classroom is the instructors' ability to creatively combine theory with practical classroom experience (Pathak, 2021). Therefore, new discoveries and ideas must be used realistically to successfully teach and learn in a classroom. Research is necessary to comprehend the laws, customs, teaching methods, course content, and stakeholder participation that help students achieve their academic potential (Chutia et al., 2022). The educators will identify components of educational programmes that effectively support advanced theoretical knowledge and skills via innovative research. Research and development play a significant role in innovation (Das & Barman, 2023). It is a financial investment in technology and conceivable future capabilities to produce new products, processes, and services. The complete

development of students may be made feasible by investigation, study, and innovation in the field of education (Kumar et al., 2020).

NEP-2020 asserts that instructors serve as facilitators for students in the modern educational environment. By continually enhancing their knowledge and proficiency in the subject area, the instructors assist the students in becoming better individuals (Umare et al., 2022). Therefore, research and innovation are vital for educational institutions in India, notably higher education institutions. The world's finest universities have repeatedly shown that the most significant higher education teaching and learning occur in environments with a strong culture of research and knowledge production; conversely, most of the best research in the world has been conducted in interdisciplinary university settings (Indhu, 2022). Professional perspectives claim that innovation makes the educational system more dynamic. The relevance of vocational education is rising in the current educational system. Vocational training is being improved through innovative educational strategies. According to the Report on the UNESCO Forum on Higher Education, Research and Innovation (2001-2009), research is prioritised in various settings, including universities and the private sector, in countries with solid innovation systems (Aithal & Aithal, 2020). As a result of the changing external environment, governments of OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) Member countries have lately given research a level of importance never before given to it as a critical engine for national development. Innovations in education, as well as theory and practice of teaching and learning, should prioritise the needs of students, parents, the community, society, and its culture. Technology applications need a solid theoretical underpinning based on systematised, focussed research and efficient education. Research and innovation on learning's cost and efficiency in terms of time may be significant (Chattopadhyay, 2021).

An instructional strategy is a theory, command, or overall teaching, testing, and evaluation scheme.

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One of the teaching approaches is one of the essential components of providing instruction for accomplishing educational objectives is an instructional strategy, which might be an idea, direction, method, or overall plan (Nölting et al., 2020). To create a more successful instructional design, it is necessary to look at the learners, learning goals, resources, learning context, overall context, situation, and lecturers' abilities in choosing the learning principles, approach, and setting. When creating instructional strategies, the learning styles of both lecturers and students are considered (Khyat, 2020). The usual instructional strategy based on design-based learning, problem-solving, creative problem-solving, creative thinking, research-based knowledge, problem-based learning, project-based learning, science, or unique teaching techniques may provide creative, innovative education. It is also essential to emphasise instruction that uses practical applications (Banerjee et al., 2021). These instructional approaches have in common starting with challenges, finding answers, testing, and assessing are all techniques and elements.

Additionally, by using numerous exciting concepts to find possible solutions to the difficulties, brainstorming is fostered, and learners are helped to develop new ideas. According to Aithal & Aithal, (2020), human resources, learning organisation, technology, regulation and system organisation, and educational research and development are the foundations of innovation and improvement in education. Therefore, this investigation highlighted the research and innovations for transformative higher education in the context of National Education Policy 2020. The study also sums up the challenges of research and innovations in education.

Research and Innovation in Education

Innovation is built on curiosity, risk-taking, and experimenting to test assumptions. Innovation is built on questioning and critiquing the current status quo (Sontakke et al., 2022). It also depends on identifying an opportunity and taking advantage of it. Education-related innovation may take on a variety of forms. It is necessary to conduct and organise research since innovation is its result (Umachagi & Selvi, 2022). Innovation is the result of research, which is the first stage. Innovation is the effective use of this information, while research may be described as the science of invention. Each higher

education institution (HEI) must create and include a system of numerous factors in its Institutional Development Plan (IDP). Innovations in pedagogy, the calibre and effect of research, professional development performance evaluations, peer and student reviews, teaching and other activities, and various types of contribution to the institution and the community, must all be included (Das & Barman, 2021). Research and innovation in education support students' flexible, professional growth. The students can be multitaskers interested in how the educational profession is evolving. The innovative corpus of knowledge has made a substantial contribution to high-quality education. Innovative education strongly emphasises societal benefits (Das, 2022). The competitive world encourages inquiry-based and creative learning, diversifying the educational process (Suryanarayana & Kumar, 2020). Therefore, this study supports the growth of innovative problem-solving abilities for tackling organised, targeted solutions to academic problems.

NEP 2020: Research and Innovations for Transforming Education

The NEP 2020 examined the changing culture of the traditional educational system. The teaching-learning process has been centered on the needs and interests of the students throughout the last ten years (Sharma & Sharma, 2022). Education is now more valuable than it formerly was. Students' confidence has been better fostered by their education. Getting a degree is not the only outcome of education, and the vocational education system is one of the most innovative. Early professional foundation building is facilitated by vocational education. Students are encouraged to discover new methods to spend time via innovative instructional practices (Kumar, 2022). The Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship and the Indian Ministry of Education are supported in their efforts to improve the educational system via NEP 2020 (Pandey & Singh, 2021). The following techniques are essential for in-depth research and educational innovation: Multiple entry-exit systems, Academic Bank of Credit, NISHTHA, NIPUN Bharat, Vidya Pravesh, SamgraShiksha (Learning Enhancement Package by SamgraShiksha), Dual, joint, and twinning degrees One class one TV channel, PM e-Vidya Diksha (2.9 lakh online e-Contents in 33 Indian languages), SWAYAM, Swayam Prabha, The emphasis on Indian languages in engineering colleges and

JEE-NEET exams, 13 Indian knowledge system centers, vocational courses at IGNOU or NIOS, PM GatiShakti, Skills hub centers at IITs, and other initiatives are just a few examples. In order to allay their fears, the current educational system encourages pupils to ask questions without reluctance (Goel & Goel, 2021). The following paragraphs explore the creative policies and practices for fostering research and innovations:

- **NISHTHA and NIPUN Bharat**

NISHTHA (National Initiative for School Heads and Teachers’ Holistic Advancement) is the world’s most significant teacher-training initiative. It is an initiative called “Improving Quality of School Education through Integrated Teacher Training” that seeks to build capacity. It was created to improve learning results for primary students. The main objective of this intensive training programme is to encourage and provide instructors with the resources they need to nurture and support students’ critical thinking. Additionally, as part of the Samagra Shiksha scheme, a comprehensive programme for the school education sector that runs from preschool through class 12, the union education ministry launched the NIPUN Bharat Mission, or the National Initiative for Proficiency in Reading with Understanding and Numeracy. The National Education Policy 2020 is in accordance with it. Every student in India’s classes 1 through 3 will be able to display FLN (Foundational Literacy and Numeracy) abilities by the end of 2026, and more encouraging outcomes have been seen after the start of NEP-2020 (Gupta, 2021).

- **Multiple entry-exit methods and the Academic Bank of Credit**

The Academic Bank of Credit (ABC) was introduced by Prime Minister Narendra Modi on July 29 as part of the first year of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. The University Grants Commission (UGC) has developed the ABC, where students will have several access and departure options. This will allow students enrolled in undergraduate (UG) and postgraduate (PG) courses to quit the course and come back within a specific period. Since academic curricula are adaptable, students may find jobs upon attaining any level of proficiency and can continue their studies when it is feasible. They can do this to further their education, reduce

dropout rates, and increase the higher education sector’s Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER). The Academic Bank of Credit (ABC), a virtual/digital repository, also details the credits that particular students have earned during their academic careers. Students will have a variety of alternatives for joining and exiting colleges or universities, as well as the capacity to set up an account (Gupta & Gupta, 2021).

- **Vidya Pravesh**

The goal is to support instructors in ensuring that children are exposed to a warm and safe atmosphere when they enter the school, allowing their smooth transition, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic (Idnani, 2021).

- **PM e-Vidya**

The Ministry of Education’s (MOE) Pradhan Mantri e-Vidya project will make it easier for students and teachers to access digital/online learning and various instructional resources. The PM e-Vidya scheme has been launched by the Indian government. This proposal states that after May 30, 2020, students can take online courses at the top 100 universities in the country.

- **Samagra Shiksha**

Samagra Shiksha is a comprehensive educational plan available for pre-kindergarten through grade twelve students. The strategy aimed to improve schools’ performance as measured by fair learning outcomes and equal access to education. The programme’s primary goals include universal access, equity, and quality, promoting rationalisation of education, and strengthening teacher education institutions (TEIS) (Gupta & Gupta, 2022).

- **One class, one TV channel**

The Union Education Ministry launched the “one class, one TV channel” project to provide persons without internet connection with access to radio and DTH channels. The education sector was among those most severely impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic since schools were closed for over two years (Das & Sarkar, 2022).

- **Twining, dual, and integrated degrees**

Indian and foreign institutions will work together to develop twinning courses. International

higher education institutions will collaborate to develop a dual degree course. A student can pursue two degrees in the same field with equivalent coursework requirements using these programs.

- **Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing and Analysis (DIKSHA)**

An initiative of the National Council for Educational Research and Training (NCERT) under the direction of the MoE, Government of India, DIKSHA is a nationwide platform for school education. Nearly all States, Union Territories, and federal autonomous bodies/boards, including CBSE, have adopted DIKSHA since it was introduced in 2017 by the Honourable M. Venkaiah Naidu, Vice President of India. The CBSE wants to educate instructors in experiential learning using the Diksha platform, an innovative pedagogical strategy. This was done to ensure the CBSE instructors used the most effective teaching methods available so that the students could quickly acquire and grasp information. The foundation of DIKSHA is made up of open-source technology developed by and for India using internet-scale technologies. This technology offers numerous use cases and solutions for teaching and learning.

- **PM Gati Shakti**

The Prime Minister introduced PM Gati Shakti, a National Master Plan for Multi-modal Connectivity that functions as a digital platform to bring together 16 Ministries, including the Roads and Railways, for integrated planning and coordinated execution of infrastructure connectivity projects. People, commodities, and services can travel from one mode of transit to another thanks to the multi-modal connection, providing integrated and seamless connectivity. It will speed up last-mile infrastructure connection and reduce people's journey time. The infrastructure plans of several Ministries and State Governments, including Bharatmala, Sagarmala, inland waterways, dry/land ports, UDAN, etc., would be included by PM Gati Shakti. On July 4, 2021, PM Modi unveiled the Gati Shakti initiative. The release of this master plan took place on October 13, 2021. A ground-breaking initiative, the PM Gati Shakti programme will enable co-operation between several ministries, states, and agencies, streamline

planning, and reduce total implementation costs (Singh & Baghel, 2020).

- **SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds) and Swayam Prabha**

The Ministry of Human Resource Development established SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds) and Swayam Prabha on July 9, 2017, to provide a comprehensive platform and gateway for online courses. This comprises all higher education courses and courses in particular skill sets. The objective is to ensure that every student in the country can access the best affordable higher education available. The SWAYAM Prabha scheme, run by the Ministry of Human Resources Development, intends to provide 32 High-Quality Educational Channels through DTH 24/7 across the country. It provides education based on curricula in a range of areas. This aims to provide access to top-notch educational resources in remote areas where internet connectivity is still problematic.

- **Vocational Education**

Education that prepares students for careers that are traditionally non-academic and entirely related to a particular trade, occupation, or vocation is known as vocational education. This type of education is also called vocational education and training (VET), career and technical education (CTE), and other similar terms. It is frequently referred to as technical education since the student obtains hands-on expertise with a particular set of techniques or technology. Comprehensive vocational education is included in the curriculum. The primary advantage of vocational education is that it creates positive links between theoretical and abstract notions, breaking up the routine of conventional education.

These are the government initiatives that give education research and innovation a higher priority. This may make it possible for the pupils' overall improvement.

The Process of Higher Education and NEP--2020

Recognising and developing each student's unique strengths while developing critical and creative thinking abilities to enable rational decision-making and creativity are the fundamental principles

of the National Education Policy. Additionally, it extensively uses technology for teaching and learning, reducing challenges associated with organising and managing education and linguistic difficulties (Kathi et al., 2022). It promotes the idea that outstanding research should come before excellent training and execution. By providing creativity and invention equal standing, the strategy seeks to transform India into a vibrant knowledge society while simultaneously improving the bar for education (Lata et al., 2022).

With the aid of technology and innovation, the Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programmes of the National Institute of Open Schooling (NIOS) and State Open Schools will be strengthened and expanded to meet better the educational needs of Indian youth who are unable to continue their education through traditional school. To bridge the achievement gap in learning outcomes, classroom activities will switch to competency-based learning and teaching (Shukla et al., 2022). The teaching of many languages will be improved via innovative and hands-on methods. Gamification, applications, and cultural aspects of the languages, such as film, theatre, storytelling, poetry, music etc., may all be included. It will be suggested that top-performing Indian colleges establish campuses overseas. Similarly, select universities, such as those among the top 100 in the world, would be supported in their efforts to operate in India (Das, 2023).

Additionally, actions will be taken to support children from SEDGs, particularly SC, ST, and OBC, in their academic success. This is to encourage more innovation and a more excellent range of courses. Throughout the academic years, with the foundational stage as the starting point, mathematics, and computational thinking will be given priority in different ways. It will be essential to know them for jobs requiring artificial intelligence. The strategy strongly emphasises the significance of higher education as the basis for knowledge creation and innovation, both of which support the expansion of the nation's economy. Consequently, the nation will be more prosperous, productive, innovative, and forward-thinking. Higher education institutions will significantly emphasise research and innovation by building technology development centers, research frontiers, and start-up incubation (Gupta & Choubey, 2021).

HEIS will create specialised support structures and contests to promote innovation among student

communities. The government will be able to develop effective and innovative adult education programmes, furthering the critical objective of obtaining 100% literacy. Faculty members at HEIS can pursue new service, teaching, and research initiatives as they see appropriate, thanks to the policy (Saxena, 2020). They will be highly motivated and enabled to generate genuinely exceptional, creative work. Institutions and faculty will be allowed to experiment with curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment challenges within a comprehensive framework of higher education credentials designed to encourage innovation. Technical education and innovation will get more assistance from professional engineering, technology, management, architecture, town planning, pharmacy, hotel management, and other technological sectors. To provide a forum for the free exchange of ideas and the use of technology to improve learning, assessment, planning, administration, and administration of education in both secondary and higher education, the National Educational Technology Forum (NETF), an independent organisation, will be created. The current pandemic has highlighted the necessity for effective alternative education delivery methods. NEP is conscious of both the advantages and disadvantages of technology. For online or digital education, the digital divide must be closed. The plan also recommends several crucial initiatives, such as pilot programmes for online education, establishing digital infrastructure, and producing, disseminating, and preserving material (Inamdar & Parveen, 2020).

According to NEP 2020, teachers must participate in pedagogy and superior content training. By 2030, interdisciplinary colleges and universities will increasingly take over the role of teacher education. The minimum degree requirement for our instructors is a 4-year integrated B.Ed degree that includes a range of subject matter and pedagogy. Teachers will have greater latitude in their pedagogical choices to instruct how they feel will be most helpful for the children in their courses. Socio-emotional learning, which is crucial for kids' overall development, will also be emphasised by teachers. Teachers that increase classroom learning using innovative teaching strategies will be recognised. Teachers will be given the most recent innovations and developments in their professions and continual opportunities for self-improvement. These will be made accessible in various ways, including

workshops held locally, regionally, statewide, nationally, and internationally, and online courses for teacher development. Pedagogical competence and professional growth have advanced through research and innovation in teacher education. Innovative improvements have been made to well-established educational systems to enhance teaching and learning. More actively engaged pupils participate in the instructional process (Kaurav et al., 2021). The learners are exposed to more relevant knowledge. Research and innovation in education have made the system more flexible and inclusive. Technology occasionally contributes substantially to instructional innovation and research in different ways (Kumar, 2022). The instructors are responsible for identifying the student's needs and interests. It is advised for instructors to use original strategies to motivate pupils throughout the teaching-learning process. Students are improving their capacity for critical thought, problem-solving, and decision-making in their academic and personal lives. The growth of knowledge benefits both research and educational innovation. Education might benefit from innovative instructors. Self-motivation is also essential for educational research and innovation (Kurien & Chandramana, 2020).

Challenges of Research and Innovation in Education

- **Learners' and instructors' low levels of interest**

It is possible that the professors will not motivate youngsters to attempt new things. Students sometimes needed help to show a drive to independently research new concepts or brainstorm. Both instructors and students are unprepared to show creativity throughout the teaching-learning process and lack the desire to attempt something new. The emphasis of self-learning is that students investigate according to their interests. Traditional schooling may be persuaded to adhere to the standards' rules (Singh, 2020).

- **Lack of Infrastructure**

The essential infrastructural facilities, such as flexible administrative supports, necessary instruments or tools for education, etc., must be supplied for a practical and creative teaching-learning process (Kazmi & Ali, 2021). Nowadays, educational sectors do not reasonably get pricey infrastructural utilities. Therefore, Financial help

will be legitimately needed for data collecting. It is expensive to use technology or go to different locations to illustrate any concept in an original way (Venkatesham & Jagadishwar, 2022).

- **Training Requirements for Teachers**

Occupational skills necessary for the creative teaching-learning process must be improved among the instructors. Students' deeper knowledge examination may be encouraged by teachers. An innovative and heuristic approach that emphasises successful teaching-learning is provided by pedagogical knowledge (Ranjan & Mohapatra, 2023).

- **Changes in Attitudes among Students and Teachers**

The ignorance of innovative studies is one of the problems in education. It takes art to innovate in the educational sector. Raising academic standards via innovative education may encourage instructors and students to try out novel ideas. Additionally, a specific pattern of the teaching-learning process may be the focus of instructors and pupils (Maurya & Ahmed, 2020).

- **Time-consuming**

The most time-consuming activities and those that call for the greatest amount of patience are research and creative schooling.

Conclusion

Professional education must include both innovation and research. Their main objective is to go thoroughly into a subject to learn something applicable to that specific company that will be helpful to everyone. It emphasises the systematic pursuit of information to learn something new in a particular field for later application, enhancing individual educational researchers' processes and lives. It becomes significant for its promotion in numerous professions, whether linked to education, physicians, attorneys, or any other topic since it helps knowledge growth, practical improvement, and policy information. It would also be great if the experts could see possible issues with their student's learning process and devise creative remedies. Notably, the policy sought to enhance learning outcomes by including problem-solving and critical thinking and enabling schools and institutions to modify their programmes within the larger

context of the NCERT curriculum. Rote learning is replaced with holistic understanding, emphasising professional preparation in high school and college while boosting a child's life skills and cognitive, social, and emotional development. Summative assessments are to be replaced by formative evaluations. This all-encompassing approach, which encourages students to showcase their unique and creative abilities and allows them to develop them, is essential in the present and lays the foundation for a better and brighter future. The development of each person's creative potential should be emphasised in the Indian educational system as it moves towards critical and creative problem-solving. If these improvements are effectively implemented, India will ultimately emerge as an essential competitor in the world of knowledge.

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Horticulture: The Key Booster of Country's Economy

S Abdul Nazeer, Hon'ble Governor of Andhra Pradesh and Chancellor, Dr. Y S R Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, Andhra Pradesh delivered the 5th Convocation Ceremony of the Dr. Y S R Horticultural University, Venkataramannagudem, Andhra Pradesh on May 12, 2023. He said, "The changing scenario driven by globalization, climate change, and dwindling natural resources demands quality and competitive education as well as research, to meet the International standards and develop climate-resilient technologies to make horticulture more profitable. The knowledge with which you would be leaving the university would serve you as the fundamental mandate in your life. I wish you to have a passionate pursuit of excellence with a human touch. Society has high hopes for you to make horticulture a viable and profitable sector." Excerpts

The prestigious national and State-level awards won by the university, such as Best performing AICRP Centre on Biological Control, Andhra Pradesh State Bio-diversity Conservation Award, Best Extension Education Institute Award, Excellence in Skill Development Award and various awards received by the faculty and students for their excellence are a testimony of the concerted efforts of the institute.

Even though achievements of farm scientists are commendable, it is a fact that the benefits of breakthroughs made in this sector are reaching the farming community with a considerable time lag, that too only in small measure. The conventional systems of delivery and extension need to be revolutionized utilizing latest Information and Communication technologies. There is a need to invigorate farm research to cater the needs of farmers and to bring about good crop husbandry practices so that a residue free produce is made available to the consumer.

Developments in the dry regions often reflect the pervasiveness of poverty as demonstrated by growing constraints of water, land degradation, migration due to frequent droughts, malnutrition etc. which are of great concern. Technologies need to be developed to bring large areas of marginal lands in arid and semi-arid regions under cultivation. The perennial horticultural crops which are more remunerative and appear to be the best option for replacing subsistence-farming and to alleviate poverty and malnutrition in arid ecosystem.

Farm mechanization which could bring substantial improvements in productivity is constrained with fragmentation of agricultural holdings. Realizing the challenges, the overall development of horticulture thus requires synergy among the technologies, input supplies, marketing system, credit policies and institutions. The Indian

farmers deserve appreciation for making the nation self-sufficient as they have shown resilience in farming, in the face of uncertain monsoons, increased input costs, biotic and abiotic stresses, market competition with farm gate prices continuing to be static.

The university's growth is measured not in terms of mere numbers, but in terms of quality education, research and extension for the noble cause of serving farmers. Though young, the Horticultural University has made vital contributions in increasing productivity and combating biotic and abiotic stresses with its new varieties and technologies. However, there is no room for complacency and Horticultural University should become a vibrant hub at the cutting edge of research, working in close coordination with the farming community by offering them time bound and cost-effective solutions. Technology development, and providing solutions to the field problems, using indigenous technologies with refinement should be the ultimate goal of the university. Research on post-harvest management including processing and value addition should be given top priority. Innovations in mechanization, digitalization of services, protected cultivation, organic production and crop diversification deserve emphasis and attention. Hopefully, the university will focus on target-oriented, location-specific and market-driven research, as well as efficient technology transfer, to benefit all stakeholders of horticulture.

The changing scenario driven by globalization, climate change and dwindling natural resources demand quality and competitive education as well as research, to meet International standards and develop climate resilient technologies to make horticulture more profitable.

My advice to the University is to implement

the New Education Policy in the right spirit to ensure quality education and better career and entrepreneurial opportunities for the students. I suggest the university to design course curriculum in line with the requirements of the industry and other stakeholders.

I congratulate the students who have received medals and awards for their academic distinction. Above all, I would like to commend the graduating class of Dr. Y.S.R. Horticultural University for having chosen horticulture as a career, which is also going to be a way of life. You have the great privilege of staying close to a sector which is the heart beat of the nation. The experiences ahead of you would be sufficiently rewarding to compensate the challenges and hardships you have gone through during your studies. A deep sense of commitment and concern for the farmers is expected of you, and I am sure that you would live up to the expectations to face the challenges that lie ahead of you. As trained horticulturists, you have a long career ahead to make contribution to the field of horticulture and

you can always look forward to the Government, to come out with new initiatives in the form of various schemes to support your cause. I would like to see a substantial number of you becoming horticultural entrepreneurs and service providers working in rural areas invigorating the farming sector.

My best wishes to you all, for your future endeavors, which I am sure you will execute with the utmost honesty and integrity. The knowledge with which you would be leaving the university would serve you as the fundamental mandate in your life. I wish you to have a passionate pursuit of excellence with a human touch. The society has high hopes on you to make horticulture a viable and profitable sector. I very much appreciate the sincere efforts of the teachers, in moulding the students into responsible citizens of country.

Wish you all a fruitful career in the horticulture field and a strong and prosperous footing in life.

Thank you all. Jai Hind

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CAMPUS NEWS

National Conference on Multidisciplinary Research, Trends and Approaches

A two-day National Conference on 'Multidisciplinary Research Trends and Approaches' was jointly organized by Shri Khushal Das University, Hanumangarh and Rajasthan Technical Library Association (RTLA), Jaipur from January 27-28, 2024 at Shri Khushal Das University, Hanumangarh, Rajasthan. More than 300 delegates including 40 research scholars, encompassing students, Library and Information Professionals, and faculty members participated in the event. The Chief Guest of the event was ADM Hanumangarh, Dr. Dinesh Rai Sapela and Guest of Honour was Jail Superintendent, Hanumangarh, Shri Narendra Kumar Swami.

In his Inaugural Speech, Professor Ratanlal Godara, Vice Chancellor of SKD University emphasized on the title of conference and its relevance with present context of information and communication technology era. He also defined the five fundamentals of life finance, friends and family, status, good deeds and best education which are the vision of S K D University. Mr. Dinesh Juneja, Chancellor of the University revealed the journey of SKD University from its establishment and imparting education to girls and boys of Hanumangarh district and nearby area. The Convenor and Patron of Rajasthan Technical Library Association, Dr Rajkumar Bhakar discussed the role of development of library and information professional in changing dimension of information services in present digital age. He also briefed about the vision and mission of RTLA.

Conference Director, Prof DV Singh, former University Librarian, University of Delhi welcomed the gathering and highlighted the objectives of the Conference. He said that nearly 50 research papers are being presented in four scheduled sessions in the conference and about 300 participants were physically present on the venue of conference. In addition to this, an online session was planned for distance scholars to present their research article. He also highlighted the relevance of the event for research scholars of various domain of knowledge, viz. humanities engineering social science medical management, in the present context. He also urged delegates to take benefit of this national-level event.

Executive Director Research and Development of SKD University, Dr. Shashi Maroliya discussed the research process at S K D University. She also talked about enrollment in research degrees. She motivated scholars for Library searches instead of Google searches. The inaugural session was concluded with the Vote of Thanks proposed by Organizing Secretary Mr. Kumar Abbas.

After the Inauguration, Dr. Anita Jain, Librarian, JECRC Jaipur chaired the technical session which was Co-chaired by Dr. Vinay Singh Kashyap, University's College Librarian, SKNA University, Jobner. Ms Vinita Chauhan, University College Librarian, SKNA University, Jobner was the rapporteur of the session.

The four invited talks were also presented in this session. The first talk was delivered by Dr. Narendra Chauhan, Associate Professor from the Guru Jambheshwar University of Technology and Science Hisar on 'Open Source Resources and Plagiarism and Its Issues'. He listed a number of open sources available on the internet. He also discussed plagiarism detection tools and their challenges and issues. The second invited talk was presented by Dr. Vinay Singh Kashyap. She talked about citation ethics and plagiarism. She focused on the basic difference between similarity and plagiarism, how to cite work in text, and why it is required. She said that there shall be no need to check similarity if every research scholar or author follows a code of conduct in the research. She also discussed the tools and techniques viz. Zotero, Mendeley, Grammarly, Cirw me, Ref me, Endnote, Latex, Turnitin, and Drill bit for research writing and checking similarity. The third talk was by Mr. Umesh Sharma on how to select a research topic/question. He discussed how librarians can help scholars in Library search. The fourth talk was given by Prof R P Singh, Govt. College for Women, Narnaul, Haryana on research in English literature. He discussed various examples of the trends in ancient research and current research.

The first session was consistent with six research papers by scholars on various topics as artificial intelligence-based library services a sustainable approach to the academic library by Miss Neelam Nautiyal and Dr Vinay Singh Kashyap, marketing of library services, resources and overview by Dr. Roshan Lal, open access publishing and academic libraries

and overview of the current scenario in Rajasthan by Sobhagyawati Gupta and Dr. Sunil Sharma, The digital revolution a close look at innovation in library services by Dr. Anamika Mathur and Dr. Shraddha Kalla. Unlocking the power of knowledge repositories' impact on institutional ranking and accredits process was delivered by Dr. Seema Sharma and Mr. Qmar Abbas and Current and future challenges research trends was delivered by Dr. Ruchi Sharma. The session was concluded with the Vote of Thanks.

The next technical session was chaired by Dr. Roshan Chaudhary, co-chaired by Mr. Umesh Sharma and the rapporteur was Ms Sobhagyavati Gupta, Sr. Assistant Librarian, Central University of Rajasthan. In this session, seven technical papers on important topics were presented by the subject experts, namely Mapping of Research Productivity of the North East Regional Institute of Education, NCERT: A Bibliometric Analysis by Ms Pooja Jain, NCERT, New Delhi and Dr. Meera, Study of the Use of E-resources by faculty members of SBN PG College, Jaipur by Ms Heeramani Dadhich and Manju Jopat, Mr Qumar Abbas on 'Practice of Quality Research Paper: Some Steps and Guidelines'. Further, Ms Omvati Sharma, Research Scholar of SKDU presented a paper on 'Navigating the Digital Landscape: A Comparative Analysis of Traditional and Electronic Reading Practices in Engineering Education'. Ms Triveni Sharma, Research Scholar of SKDU with Dr Bhakar and Dr Bhoop Singh presented his paper on 'A Bird Eye's View of Electronic Resources of India' and Mr. Om Prakash Vaishnav, Research Scholar, SKDU presented his paper on 'Important Obstacles during Research for the Beginners'. The last paper of this session and the day was presented by Mr. Manish Sharma, Librarian, Govt. Medical College, Patiala on 'The Advantage of being the ABC Identification System in Higher Education. The session was concluded with Vote of Thanks.

The next session was Chaired by Mr. Om Prakash Vaishnav, College Librarian, Ajmer, Co-chaired by Dr. Shraddha Kalla, Librarian, IIMR, University Jaipur and the rapporteur was Dr. D R Bhincher, Librarian, SKIT Jaipur. The first paper was presented on 'Information Communication Services in Library Access to Children With Special Needs by Sangeeta Panwar and Dr Rajkumar Bhakar. The next paper was presented by Ms. Kailash Kanwar, Research Scholar, SKD University on 'Sustainable Development Goals'. Ms. Sushma Goswami, Assistant Librarian, SKD University on 'Importance of Library Networks

in India'. In the session, the first special talk was delivered by Dr. Bhoop Singh, Librarian, Bhartiya Skill Development University Jaipur on the topic of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Research Scholars. He discussed the various research assistant tools like bibliographic tools, journal finder tools, literature mapping tools, reference management tools, antiplagiarism tools, and research visibility tools. The second talk was delivered by Dr. Vinita Chauhan, Assistant Librarian, Shri Karan Narendra Agriculture University on the challenges of early career researchers. She highlighted the do's and don'ts in Research. The third talk was delivered by Dr. Mukesh Pathak, Deputy Librarian, School of Planning and Architecture Bhopal on 'Research Data Citation and Management. He briefed about raw data and its reuse and data management of data sets in research. The next invited talk was presented by Shobhagyawati Gupta, Senior Assistant Librarian, Central University of Rajasthan on 'Research Support Services by University Library and LIS Professionals'. The fourth session was the online session. The paper presenters were Prof. Manak Chand Soni, Dean, Faculty of Commerce and Management, SKDU, Ms. Madhubala, Dr Bharti Taldar, Ms. Neha Bhadoo and Ms Jyoti Mishra, from different research domains.

In the Valedictory Session, Dr. Arun Kumar, Vice Chancellor of Swami Keshwanand Agriculture University, Bikaner said that research plays a significant role in accreditations as well as the competitiveness of the university, which ultimately enables it to attract top talent in terms of both students and faculty. After the New Education Policy, multidisciplinary research can solve many of the major challenges effective research has faced in the decade. This cooperative and coordinated research requires the unified efforts of experts from different disciplines.

Prof Kumar also clarion calls to Librarian that Libraries can also lift their institutions to a higher plane of multidisciplinary collaboration by leveraging their place in higher education to become the hub of multidisciplinary activity, where librarians foster innovative models of teaching, learning, research, conversation, reflection, and engagement.

Dr. Sanjay Mishra, Dean of Student's Welfare proposed the Vote of Thanks and wished everyone a great time ahead. He assured the participants to continue holding such academic gatherings and talks in the future on different topics of high importance in the Research and Development.

International Conference on Perspectives and Innovations in Open and Distance Learning

A three-day International Conference on ‘Perspectives and Innovations in Open and Distance Learning’ is being organized by the National Institute of Open Schooling, Noida in collaboration with the Commonwealth Educational Media Centre for Asia (CEMCA) from April 01-03, 2024 through Hybrid Mode. This conference aims to bring together educators, researchers, policymakers, and industry experts to share insights, best practices, and cutting-edge innovations that are shaping the future perspectives of ODL.

Open and Distance Learning is evolving as an appropriate alternative for heterogeneous society. Besides general clientele, it makes earnest efforts to reach the unreached. It is known as flexible, inclusive, and adaptive to the diverse needs of the learners. In the present era, learners are rapidly involved in technological, social, and economic environments. They need to have multitasking skills, global connections, recognition, cultural sensitivity, and collaborative and social skills. Therefore, it is important to design an education system for educators, policymakers, and educational institutions to provide relevant and effective learning experiences according to the needs of the learners.

The need for lifelong learning is significant and relevant in ODL mode through technological advancement, changing work dynamics in the contemporary context. The present scenario of ODL offers a variety of emerging trends such as providing personalized learning experiences, integration of data analysis tools, infusing artificial intelligence to automate administrative tasks, providing insights into course improvements, and delivering smart content that is adaptable to various learning styles, etc. The innovations in the form of a hybrid learning approach help to address the desire for flexibility among learners while allowing them to balance the advantages of online learning with periodic face-to-face interactions. The innovative approaches and perspectives in the ODL are contributing to creating a virtual environment and comprehensive transformation. Open Distance Learning has the potential to democratize education by providing access to diverse learners. The conference will initiate dialogues and emphasize discussions on ensuring

inclusivity, and accessibility and addressing the digital divide in ODL. The Subthemes of the event are:

- Perspectives and Innovations in ODL.
- Policy frameworks and practices supporting ODL.
- Technology-Enhanced Learning in ODL.
- Pedagogical and Administrative Strategies in ODL.
- Inclusive Access, Equity and Quality in ODL.
- Vocational Education through ODL mode.
- Collaboration and Networking in ODL.

For further details, contact Dr. Alok Kumar Gupta, Deputy Director (Acad./CBC), National Institute of Open Schooling, A-24-25, Institutional Area, Sector-62, Noida (U.P.), Mobile No: 09818936966, E-mail: ddebc@nios.ac.in. For updates, log on to: www.nios.ac.in.

International Webinar on Labour Law Enforcement

A two-day International Webinar on ‘Labour Law Enforcement: Challenges and Remedies’ is being jointly organized by the Labour Law Institutions-National and International and 07 National Law Universities from March 30-31, 2024.

There is no dearth of Labour Laws to protect workers in organized and unorganized sectors across the globe. However, there is a dearth of quality administration, governance, and enforcement of Labour laws meant to protect workers in one form or another. The State Agencies created by the governments for Labour law governance and enforcement are also reluctant to enforce Labour law in their respective jurisdiction. Liberalisation, privatisation and globalization, up to some extent, are also responsible for diluting the enforcement of Labour law for the promotion of trade and business by ignoring the sustainable development of all the stakeholders involved in the production, distribution, or supply of goods and services in all the sectors across the globe. Workers’ associations or Unions have also failed to ensure strict compliance with Labour laws. The Subthemes of the Event are:

- The dearth of Empirical data to evaluate the effectiveness of enforcement of labour laws.
- A dearth of Labour law Enforcement Infrastructure-skilled manpower, IT infrastructure, etc. for effective and quality governance of Labour law.

- Dilution of Inspection system for industrial development and enforcement of Labour law.
- Effectiveness of the Labour tribunals in providing speedy and economical justice.
- Empowering workers for demanding Labour law enforcement.
- Enforcement of Labour rights through Civil proceedings: Effectiveness.
- Enforcement of law through criminal prosecution proceedings: Effectiveness.
- Impact of Liberalization, Privatization and globalization on enforcement, and administration of Labour law.
- Labour Administration of Social Security Schemes in Organized and Unorganized Sector Workers: ESI, EPF, ECA, PGA, MBA, MNREGA, etc.,
- Labour Law Administration of Industrial Relations- IDA, TUs, etc.
- Labour Law Administration of Labour Welfare Measures- Workers' Welfare Boards, Statutory and Voluntary Welfare Schemes, etc.
- Labour Law Administration of Law Governing OSH- Safety, health, Occupational and Employment Injury.
- Labour Law Administration of Law Governing Wage- Bonus, Minimum wages, Equal Remuneration.
- Labour law Controlling/facilitating Contract workers; Administration and Enforcement.
- Liability of Principal Employers and Labour Contractors for enforcement of Labour law
- Liability of the State in diluting quality enforcement of Labour law.
- Quality of enforcement of OSH rights by DGFASLI, etc.
- Role of ILO in Promoting Meticulous compliance and enforcement of Labour Laws.
- Role of the Judiciary in enforcing workers' rights.
- Role of the State- Central and State Labour administrative Agencies in quality Enforcement of Labour Laws.
- Role of Trade Unions in supporting/coercing Labour law enforcement.
- Any other topic directly or indirectly related to the administration, governance and enforcement of Labour law.

For further details, contact Mr. J S Mann, Centre for Transparency and Accountability in Governance, National Law University, Sector 14, Dwarka, New Delhi – 110078. E-mail: ctag@nludelhi.ac.in. For updates, log on to: www.nludelhi.ac.in/events

AIU News

West Zone Student Research Convention—*ANVESHAN 2023*

A two-day West Zone Student Research Convention— *ANVESHAN 2023* was jointly organized by the Association of Indian Universities (AIU), New Delhi and the Department of Computer Science & the Department of Students Development, Shivaji University, Kolhapur (SUK), Maharashtra from December 28-29, 2023. The *ANVESHAN* provides an opportunity for university students worldwide to co-develop and co-present innovative ideas in partnership with university students in India.

The event was inaugurated by Vice Chancellor, Prof. D T Shirke and Dr. Amarendra Pani, Joint Director and Director(I/c) Research Division, AIU in the presence of Prof. P S Patil, Pro-Vice Chancellor,

Dr. Usha Rai Negi, Assistant Director, Research Division, AIU, Dr. V N Shinde, Registrar, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Dr. M S Deshmukh, Dean, Faculty of Humanities, Dr. P T Gaikwad, Director of Department of Student's Development. Around 11 universities, 64 projects and 106 students from Maharashtra and Gujarat participated in the event. The event was categorized into 6 areas, i.e. Agriculture, Basic Sciences, Engineering & Technology, Health Sciences and Allied Subjects, Pharmacy, Nutrition, Social Sciences, Humanities, Commerce and Law, and Interdisciplinary Research. The event included research projects based on innovative concepts from graduate level to PhD researchers. The research projects were presented under various fields of Basic and Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology, Agriculture and Allied Fields, Health Sciences and Allied Fields,

Social Sciences, Humanities, Commerce, Business Management, and Law. These include Biosensors, Automated Harvesting Machines, Sensory Chairs, Advanced Technology Bulbs, Modern Aero-Cells, Pharma ATMs for Medicines, Pipeline Fault Detectors, Electricity Prepaid Meters, Power Theft Detectors, Advanced Thin Film Deposition, Medicinal Scented Candles, Alambi Saka. Various targeted research projects and posters included 3-D printing, making pots from grass and fibre roots, auto compostable sanitary pads, sleeping bags for children in rural areas, drug delivery gel through the nose to the brain, gender-neutral Oshtha Shalaka, the pension scheme for farmers. Many of these researches have even gone as far as patents.

The PowerPoint presentation was done to focus the projects from a different angle. The event was followed by the Valedictory Function. The Valedictory Function was graced by Vice Chancellor, Prof. D T Shirke and Dr. Amarendra Pani in the presence of other dignitaries.

Dr. Pani said that the Exploration Research Festival is emerging as a popular forum among the research youth across the country. Before 2007, there was no research, innovation or innovation promotion competition in the country except for the Invention Research Competition in Maharashtra. To address this shortcoming, the Federation of Indian Universities started organizing Exploratory Research Festivals across the country. It is getting a huge response from the young researchers of the country and quality research have been realized through it. He informed that the scope of this competition is now being extended to the international level and it

will be organized in three ways as national research competition in which international research students will participate, an international competition in which national researchers will participate and national and international youth researchers will also be able to participate individually.

The Vice Chancellor, Prof. DT Shirke said that when researching a topic, we answer many questions easily. However, young researchers should try to find the answers to the simple questions of common people, which we cannot answer so easily, in the future life. Instead of running away from troubling questions, face them head-on. Development is a very broad concept. He also urged that every researcher should find the definition of development for his own research and work to achieve that development.

On this occasion, Pro-Vice Chancellor Prof. P S Patil said that young researchers should try to convert the innovative concepts presented in the research festival into socially useful technologies and low-cost commercial applications. Dr. V N Shinde, Registrar and Dr. P T Gaikwad, Director, Department of Students Development present. Initially, Dr. Kavita Oza welcomed and introduced the Chief Guest, followed by Dr. K G Kharade who presented a brief report of the event. Dr. Rajendra Atigre announced the results of all the categories. Ms. Shruti Bhapkar worked as an anchor of the valedictory event, while Dr. V S Kumbhar proposed a Vote of Thanks. A large number of subject experts, team heads, examiners from all over the country, teachers from the coordinating team, administrative servants, and research students from two states of the western region attended the event. A group photo was taken after the valedictory function.

Category-wise Result of the *ANVESHAN* Humanities, Social Sciences

Rank	Name of the Participants	Institute Name	Title
1	i) Khedkar Prathamesh Pandit	Savitribai Phule Pune University	Innovative Onion Storage Management
2	i) Pandey Gaurav Onkarnath ii) Jagatkar Rutuja Nagsen iii) Kumari Sneha iv) Kewalramani Ginni Sunil	University of Mumbai	ऑचल: A Reusable, Eco-friendly Sleeping Bag for Battling Neonatal Hypothermia in Rural Areas
3	i) Harshali Rathod ii) Shivani Narsikar iii) Prem Bidve	MGM University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar, Aurangabad	Green Synthesis Of Nanoparticles By Using Carica Papaya And To Study Their Biochemical Applications

Health Sciences Category

Rank	Name of the Participants	Institute Name	Title
1	i) Sopan N Nangare	Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon	Fabrication of Surface Decorated Graphene Oxide Nanocomposites for Label Free Prognosis of Alzheimer's Disease
2	i) Mahale Manas Moreshwar	University of Mumbai	Masked Language Models are Fragment Based Drug Designers
3	i) Anushka Vishwanath Shinde ii) Shreya Uday Lohakare iii) Nikhil Pratap Marathe	Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, Maharashtra	SILOSTAT - AN Innovative Lifesaving Hemostat for Emergency Situations

Basic Science

Rank	Name of the Participants	Institute Name	Title
1.	i) Ms Sargun Tushar Basrani	D. Y Patil Education Society, Deemed to be University, Kolhapur	Mefloquine as Inhibitor of Ergosterol Biosynthesis Pathway in Candida Albicans
2.	i) Avanti Atul Puranik ii) Shrawani Deepak Nighot iii) Pradnya Mahavir Magdum	Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune	REVIGREEN - An Auto-Compostable Sanitary Pad for Green Earth
3.	i) Surjeet Ghanshyam Adagale	Shivaji University, Kolhapur	Synthesizing Bioplastic and Vegan Leather

Engineering and Technology

Rank	Name of the Participants	Institute Name	Title
1.	i) Leena Rajendra Chaudhari	D. Y. Patil Education Society, (Deemed- to-be-University), Kolhapur	Tissue Engineered Ear Pinna
2.	i) Tony Tom Thomas ii) Justina Chetan Chaturvedi iii) Razi shaikh	Dr. Homi Bhabha State University, Mumbai	Advancing Thin Film Deposition: Designing and Fabrication of an Automated Silar-CBD Instrument with PC Interface
3.	i) Patel Deepkumar Jayeshbhai ii) Patel Manan Navinbhai iii) Patel Zeel Shaileshbhai iv) Patel Hilay Mukeshbhai	Ganpat University	Pipeline Inspection Device

Agriculture

Rank	Name of the Participants	Institute Name	Title
1.	i) Yadav Om Manoj	University of Mumbai	SacoPeatTM: A Novel Potting Media
2.	i) Shankar More ii) Sainath Suryawanshi	Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University, Nanded	Novel Film Forming Spray for the Treatment of Mastitis in Cows
3.	i) Bhavik D Chaudhary ii) Dhruv S Soni., Patel iii) Mitkumar Daxeshkumar iv) Amin Sahil Bakulbhai	Ganpat University	Extraction of Material from Mushroom Residue for 3D Printing

Interdisciplinary Research

Rank	Name of the Participants	Institute Name	Title
1.	i) Thombare Namadev Bhagwan	Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune	Agro-based Weeding Machine
2.	i) Sanket Pawar ii) Deepanshu Sharma iii) Mawwiz Shaikh	MGM University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar, Aurangabad	Tongue Operated Wheelchair
3.	i) Tejas Patil	Kavayitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon	Happy Feet: Pedicure Nail Lacquer for Animal Foot Infections

After the completion of the event, a feedback form was shared with the participants and mentors, and the following observations were seen:

- 54.2% of participants were pleased with the event's location while 25% of participants thought that the venue was excellent. 16.7% of participants were dissatisfied with the event's location while 4.1% of participants thought the venue was average.
- It was found that 41.7% of participants were extremely satisfied with the catering and food options indicating that they were very pleased with the event's location. 33.3% of participants thought the menu was satisfactory while 25% of participants thought the menu was neutral.
- Around 44.4.7% of participants were extremely satisfied, indicating that they were pleased with the accommodation facility. The accommodation facility satisfied 38.9% of the participants. 8.3% of participants were dissatisfied with the accommodation facility.
- 47.2% of participants were extremely satisfied, indicating that they were very pleased with the transport facility. 33.3% of participants were satisfied with the transport facility and 16.7% of participants thought the transport facility was neutral.
- 47.2% of participants stated that the experts were excellent in their field. Expert expertise was rated as good by 19.4% of participants, average by 16.7%, and very poor by 11.1% of participants.
- 52.8.2% of participants said the overall experience was excellent. Overall experience was rated as good by 27.8% of participants, average of 16.7%.
- If such events are organized in the future, 69.4% of participants intend to attend and around 16.7% of participants are also interested in attending the event. 8.3% of participants are unsure whether they will attend such events in the future, but 5.6% will most likely not attend.
- 75.0% of participants said that the staff was very helpful and friendly. 16.7% of participants rated their overall experience as good, while 5.6% rated it as average. Overall 75% participants highly appreciated the event. □

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THESES OF THE MONTH

HUMANITIES

A List of doctoral theses accepted by Indian Universities
(Notifications received in AIU during the month of Jan-Feb, 2024)

Geography

1. Begum, Kashmiri. **Meander dynamics of lower Disang River, Assam.** (Prof. S K De), Department of Geography, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
2. Himanshi. **Women employment in organized and unorganized sectors in Haryana: A socio-spatial analysis.** (Dr. Rajeshwari), Department of Geography, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.

History

1. Jadeja, Urvashiba Aniruddhsinh. **Wankaner Nagarpalika: A historical study (1950-2015 A D).** (Dr. Smitaben S Zala), Department of History, Saurashtra University, Rajkot.
2. Momin, Binea M. **Material culture and social formation in the Southern Bank of the Brahmaputra with reference to the Garo.** (Prof. Aparna Mathur), Department of History, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
3. Nonglait, Rishababiang L. **Women organisations and activism in Khasi-Jaintia Hills: A historical study.** (Prof. A N Passah), Department of History, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
4. Patel, Daxaben Dhirubhai. **The contribution of Valsad District's in freedom movement of India (1915 to 1947).** (Dr. Smitaben S Zala), Department of History, Saurashtra University, Rajkot.
5. Sangma, Tokse Karen D. **Ethnicity and material culture of the Garo: An ethno-historical study.** (Dr. Tilok Thakuria), Department of History and Archaeology, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
6. Syiem, Tennyson. **A historical study of Ri-Bhoi from pre-colonial to contemporary times.** (Prof. V R Rengsi), Department of History, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.

Languages & Literature

Assamese

1. Mishra, Parishmita. **Manastattvik Tattvar adharat Manikuntala Bhattacharyar upanyas: Ek Bishleshnatamak adhyayan (Nirbasito upanyasar bishlesh ullikhanasaha).** (Dr. Ratul Deka), Department of Assamese, Bodoland University, Kokrajhar.

English

1. Barua, Rima. **Migration as travel: A study of select travel writings of Tahir Shah.** (Dr. Suranjana Choudhury), Department of English, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
2. Bhatia, Poonam. **Convergence of the public and the private world: A study of Rohinton Mistry's fiction.** (Dr. Jaibir Singh Hooda), Department of English, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak.
3. Chavda, Jignesh Manharlal. **Emergence of graphic novel in India: A critical study of its journey towards mainstream literary genre.** (Dr. Jaydipsinh Dodiya), Department of English, Saurashtra University, Rajkot.
4. Dias, Naveen Augustine Harush. **English language skills and tourism industry: A need based approach to University curriculum in Karnataka.** (Prof. Nagya Naik B H), Department of English, Kuvempu University, Shankaraghatta.
5. Jayavelu, D. **Amish Tripathy's Ramchandra series: Mapping of modern problems on ancient myth.** (Dr. Ritendra Sharma), Department of English, Indus University, Ahmedabad.
6. Mamatha, V F. **Women characters in the indigenised Shakespearean cinematic adaptations: A study of the cultural politics of gender.** (Dr. Venkata Ramani Challa), Department of English, CMR University, Bangalore.
7. Pathak, Punit Jitendra. **Re-imagining India: Representation of India in Indian diasporic writings.** (Dr. Aditi Vahia), Department of English, M S University of Baroda, Vadodara.
8. Sawhney, Arpita. **From a window less prison to an open house: Re envisioning history in Toni Morrison's select novels.** (Dr. Ram Niwas), Department of English, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.
9. Sikander Singh. **Narratological experimentations in the novels of Ashwin Sanghi.** (Prof. Deepti Dharmani), Department of English and Foreign Languages, Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa.
10. Singh, Reetu. **The problematic of identity in the novels of Khaled Hosseini.** (Prof. Deepti Dharmani), Department of English and Foreign Languages, Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa.

11. Tamanna. **Indian crime narratives: A study of selected contemporary novels in English.** (Prof. Anu Shukla), Department of English and Foreign Languages, Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa.
12. Vinod Kumar. **Patterns of subalternity in the selected novels of Amitav Ghosh.** (Prof. Pankaj Sharma), Department of English and Foreign Languages, Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa.
13. Vyas, Abheepsa Chirag. **A sense of place in African-American Community analyzed through the autobiography of Maya Angelou.** (Dr. Ritendra Sharma), Department of English, Indus University, Ahmedabad.

Gujarati

1. Shah, Sejal. **Muni Jinvijayji sampadit prachin Gujarati gadhyasandarbh: Ek adhyayan.** (Dr. Darshana Oza), Department of Gujarati, S.N.D.T. Women's University, Mumbai.

Hindi

1. Chauhan, Khumansinh Sursinh. **Udey prakash ke katha sahitye ka samikshnatamak adhyayan.** (Dr. Rekhaben Z patel), Department of Hindi, Saurashtra University, Rajkot.
2. Dhedhi, Pritiben Hansarajbhai. **Ikkisvi sadi ke pramukh nariwadi Hindi mahila upanyaskaroan ke upanyasoan ke nariwadi alochna.** (Dr. Hemal M Vyas), Department of Hindi, Saurashtra University, Rajkot.
3. Gupta, Amit Kumar. **Pravasi Hindi sahityakar Ramdev Dhurandhar ke upanyasoan mein Bhartiya sanskriti evam parivesh bodh.** (Prof. Kanubhai Ninama), Department of Hindi, M S University of Baroda, Vadodara.
4. Vadera, Dharmendrakumar Jagabhai. **Swatantryaotar adivasi jeevan kendrit chayanit Hindi upanyas kathey aur shilp.** (Dr. B K Kalasva), Department of Hindi, Saurashtra University, Rajkot.

Sanskrit

1. Bhagwat, Amita. **Tragical elements in Sanskrit drama and Shakespearean tragedy: A comparative study.** (Dr. Jitendrakumar Tiwari), Department of Sanskrit, S.N.D.T. Women's University, Mumbai.
2. Bhatti, Swati Vrajlal. **Bharat-darshana in Dr Harshdev Madhav's poems (Special reference with poems published from 2008 to 2018).** (Dr. Navnit J Joshi), Department of Sanskrit, Saurashtra University, Rajkot.
3. Chanderkla. **Durgacharye va Skand Maheshwarkrit nirukt-teekaoan ka tulnatamak adhyayan: Nirukat ke Naighuntak tatha Naigam kand ke sadarbh mein.**

(Dr. Ravi Prabhat), Department of Sanskrit, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak.

4. Dey, Sangita. **Critical edition of Jivanji Maharaj's Narsimhavijayanatakam.** (Prof. Suryamani Rath), Department of Sahitya, Central Sanskrit University, New Delhi.
5. Dixit, Ayush. **A critical study of professor Radhavallabh Tripathi's contribution to the tradition of Alankar-Shastra.** (Prof. Sanandan Kumar Tripathi), Department of Sahitya, Central Sanskrit University, New Delhi.
6. Gamit, Jayshree Ratilal. **A Literary study of Sanskrit Mahakavyas of twenty first century (2001-18).** (Dr. Sweta Prajapati), Department of Sanskrit, M S University of Baroda, Vadodara.
7. Jani, Pooja Ambarishbhai. **Srimallakshyasangitam of Chatur Pandit: A study.** (Dr. Shweta Jejurkar), Department of Sanskrit, M S University of Baroda, Vadodara.
8. Madan Lal. **Padmashriramakanta Shukla virachitanam dhvaniroopakanam sameekshatmakamadhyayanam.** (Prof. Ratan Mohan Jha), Department of Sahitya, Central Sanskrit University, New Delhi.
9. Mishra, Gyan Prakash. **Paninisutreshu prashlishtpadanam samikshatmakamadhyayanam.** (Prof. Bharat Bhooshan Tripathi), Department of Vyakarna, Central Sanskrit University, New Delhi.
10. Rishi Kumar. **Shuklayajurvedasanhitayah alankarikam adhyayanam.** (Prof. Prabhat Kumar Mohapatra), Department of Sahitya, Central Sanskrit University, New Delhi.
11. Roy, Abhijit. **Influence of Puranas on the dramas of Kalipadatarkacharya.** (Prof. Minati Rath), Department of Sahitya, Central Sanskrit University, New Delhi.
12. Somveer. **Shrimadbhagawadgeetayam vaidiksrotasamanusheelanam.** (Dr. Hanuman Mishra), Department of Shuklayajurveda, Shri Lal Bahadur Shastri Rashtriya Sanskrit Vidyapeetha, New Delhi.
13. Sonu. **Analytical study of the characterization of the antagonists in the plays of bhasa in Sanskrit literature.** (Dr. Ganesh Shankar Vidyarthi), Department of Sahitya, Central Sanskrit University, New Delhi.

Urdu

1. Tanveer, Mohd. **Print wo electronic media mein fun-E-Sahafath.** (Dr. Mohammed Abdul Qavvi), Department of Urdu, Telangana University, Nizamabad.

Linguistics

1. Lalhmingmawia. **Multilingual cityscapes of North-East India.** (Prof. S K Singh), Department of Linguistics, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.

2. Ngullie, Yantsubeni. **A descriptive grammar of Lotha.** (Dr. B Khyriem), Department of Linguistics, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
3. War, Gamidalah. **Argument structure in Pnar.** (Dr. S A Lyngdoh), Department of Linguistics, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
4. Ying, Langjaw Kyang. **A functional: Typological study of Jingpaw, a language spoken in Myanmar.** (Dr. S A Lyngdoh), Department of Linguistic, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.

Performing Arts

Music

1. Ahire, Pravin Kashinath. **Uttar Hindustani sangeet paddhati ke aprakashit, aprachalit aur navanirmit Audav-Audav, Audav-Shadav tatha Shadav-ShadavJati ke ragoan ka vishleshnatamak adhyayan.** (Dr. Ashwinikumar R Singh), Department of Music, M S University of Baroda, Vadodara.
2. Goregaonkar, Sanika. **The study of Ashtang in khyal gayaki of Gwalior Gharana.** (Dr. Sheetal More), Department of Music, S.N.D.T. Women's University, Mumbai.

3. Iyer, Narayanan P. **The potential influence of Indian music on human values.** (Dr. Meera Rajaram Pranesh), Department of Music, Jain University, Bangalore.

Visual Art

1. Narwal, Neetu. **Samkaleen bhartiye chitrekaroon kee kala ka kalatamak evam takniki adhyayan.** (Dr. Meenakshi Hooda), Department of Visual Arts, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak.

Philosophy

1. Basumatary, Jagadish. **Michel Foucault's concept of power: A phenomenological approach.** (Dr. Basil Pohlong), Department of Philosophy, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
2. Borgohain, Ivy. **Neo-Vaisnavism of Assam and Animal Rights: A critical study.** (Prof.X P Mao), Department of Philosophy, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.
3. Medhi, Nijara. **Buddhist ethics and its contemporary relevance: A critical study.** (Prof. X P Mao), Department of Philosophy, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong.

□

**Kasarde Vikas Mandal's,
KASARDE SENIOR COLLEGE
Mukkam Post - Kasarde, Tal. - Kankavali, Dist. - Sindhudurg 416 801**

APPLICATIONS ARE INVITED FOR THE FOLLOWING POSTS FROM THE ACADEMIC YEAR 2024-25:
UN-AIDED

Sr. No.	Cadre	Subject	No. of Posts	Total No. of Posts	Posts Reserved for
1	Principal	--	01	01	OPEN - 01
2	Assistant Professor	Commerce	01	01	OPEN - 01
3	Assistant Professor	Accountancy	01	01	OPEN - 01
4	Librarian	--	01	01	OPEN - 01

The posts for the reserved category candidates will be filled in by the same category candidates (Domicile of State of Maharashtra) belonging to that particular category only.

Reservation for women will be as per University Circular No. BCC/16/74/1998 dated 10th March, 1998. 4% reservation shall be for the persons with disability as per University Circular No. Special Cell/ICC/2019-20/05 dated 05* July, 2019.

Candidates having knowledge of Marathi will be preferred.

“Qualification, Pay Scales and other requirement are as prescribed by the UGC Notification dated 18th July, 2018, Government of Maharashtra Resolution No.Misc-2018/C.R.56/18/UNI-1, dated 8th March, 2019 and University circular No. TAAS/(CT)/ICD/2018-19/1241, dated 26th March, 2019 and revised from time to time”. The Government Resolution & Circular are available on the website:mu.ac.in.

Applicants who are already employed must send their application through proper channel. Applicants are required to account for breaks if any in their academic career.

Applications with full details should reach to the **CHAIRMAN, Kasarde Vikas Mandal's, Kasarde Senior College, Mukkam Post - Kasarde, Tal. - Kankavali, Dist. - Sindhudurg 416 801.** within 15 days from the date of publication of this advertisement. **This is University approved advertisement.**

Sd/-
CHAIRMAN

Vidya Prasarak Mandal, Gadhinglaj
Jagruti Shikshanshastra Mahavidyalaya,
Gadhinglaj
 Shendri Road, Gadhinglaj, Tal.- Gadhinglaj,
 Dist.-Kolhapur – 416 502 (Maharashtra)
 (Affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur)
(Permanently Non Granted)

WANTED

Applications are invited from eligible candidates for the following posts:

Sr. No.	Name of Post	Vacant Post	Reservation
1.	Principal	01	Post – 01 (Open to All)

Note:

For detailed information about posts, qualifications and other terms and conditions, please visit University website: www.unishivaji.ac.in.

**THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF ADVANCED
 LEGAL STUDIES (NUALS)**
 Kalamassery, Kerala

No. NUALS/Admn/ A3/1505/2023 Dated: 19.02.2024

NOTIFICATION FOR FACULTY POSITION

The National University of Advanced Legal Studies (NUALS) Kalamassery–683 503, Kerala, invites applications for the following Faculty position:

Professor in Law (On Deputation basis) : 1 No

For further details, visit the University website “www.nuals.ac.in”. The last date for the receipt of applications is **31.03.2024**.

REGISTRAR

Rajarshi Shahu Shikshan Sanstha, Sillod.
Yeshwantrao Chavan College of Arts, Commerce & Science,
Sillod – 431112 Tq. Sillod Dist. Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar
 (Affiliated to Dr. B.A.M.U. Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar)
 Email: yccsillod@yahoo.com • Website : <https://yccsillod.in>

WANTED

Applications are invited for the following full time aided posts of Librarian from eligible candidates. Applications duly completed in all respect should reach to the Principal, Yeshwantrao Chavan College, Sillod **within 15 days** from the date of publication of this advertisement.

Sr. No	Post	No. of vacant Post	Total No of post	Total reservation
1	Librarian	1	1	Open - 1

Conditions:

1. Permission as per NOC No. JDHE Aurangabad /NOC/2019/26 Dated: 23/02/2024 from Hon. Deputy Secretary (Higher Education), Mantralaya, Govt. of Maharashtra, Mumbai.
2. Educational qualifications, pay scales and service conditions are as prescribed by the UGC, Govt. of Maharashtra & Dr. B.A.M.U. Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar from time to time.
3. The complete application should be sent to **Principal, Yeshwantrao Chavan College of Arts, Commerce & Science, Sillod Tq. Sillod Dist. Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar. (MS) Pin – 431112**
4. Candidates who are already in service should apply through proper channel.
5. For more details visit <https://yccsillod.in>.

Dr. Ashok Pandit **Dr. Rahul Palodkar** **Shri. Prabhakar Palodkar**
 Principal Secretary President

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Phone Office: 91-11-23230059, Extn. 208/213.

BISHOP KURIALACHERRY COLLEGE FOR WOMEN, AMALAGIRI, KOTTAYAM

Amalagiri P.O., Pin-686561,
Ph: 7559097384
E-mail: bkcamala@yahoo.com
Website: www.bkcollege.ac.in
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WANTED PRINCIPAL

Applications are invited from qualified candidates for appointment to the permanent post of Principal in Bishop Kurialacherry College for Women, Amalagiri.

Age and qualification as per Government/UGC/ Mahatma Gandhi University Rules. Application forms can be had from the College Office on payment of Rs. 2000/- or can download from the College Website. Those who are downloading application form from the website should enclose a DD of Rs 2050/- favouring B K College Amalagiri. Those who have obtained degrees from other Universities should produce equivalency/ eligibility certificate from Mahatma Gandhi University. Applications with all the supporting documents should be submitted to the College office within one month of publication of this notification.

(Sd/-)Manager

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Appasaheb Birnale College of Architecture, Sangli

South Shivaji Nagar, Sangli-Miraj Road, Sangli-416 416

(0233) 2322336, 2320294

(Affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur)

(Permanently Non-Grant)

WANTED

Applications are invited from eligible candidates for the following post:

Sr. No.	Name of the Post	Vacant Posts	Reservation
01	Principal	01	Post -01 (Open to All)

Note:-

- For detailed information about post, qualifications and other terms and conditions, please Visit university website : www.unishivaji.ac.in.

Place : Sangli Chairman
Shri Vasant Rao Patil Bandu Patil Trust, Sangli.
Tal- Miraj, Dist- Sangli -416 416

Council of Education, Kolhapur Night College of Arts and Commerce, Kolhapur & Shahaji Law College, Kolhapur

(C/o D.R.K. College of Commerce, 649, 'C' Ward, Azad Chowk, Tal- Karveer, Dist- Kolhapur -416002. (M.S.)

(Affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur)

(Permanently Granted)

WANTED

Applications are invited from eligible candidates for the following posts:

	Name of Post	Total Number of Vacant Posts	Total Reservation
1.	Principal (Night College of Arts and Commerce, Kolhapur & Shahaji Law College, Kolhapur)	02	ST-01 and VJ(A)-01

Note : For detailed information about post, qualifications and other terms and conditions, please visit University website : www.unishivaji.ac.in

Place : Kolhapur

Date :

Secretary
Council of Education, Kolhapur

भारतीय शिक्षक प्रशिक्षण संस्थान
Indian Institute of Teacher Education
(A State University established by the Government of Gujarat)

AN ADVERTISEMENT FOR THE POSITION OF THE VICE-CHANCELLOR

Indian Institute of Teachers Education, is established by the Gujarat Act, 08 of 2010, referred to as IITE Act. The Search Committee is constituted as per Section 12 of the IITE Act. The Committee invites applications/nominations for the appointment of Vice-Chancellor along with the detailed bio-data.

A person possessing the highest level of competence, integrity, morals, and institutional commitment is to be appointed as Vice-Chancellor. The person to be appointed as a Vice-Chancellor should be a distinguished academician, with a minimum of ten years of experience as a Professor in a University system or ten years of experience in a reputed research and/or academic administrative organisation with proof of having demonstrated academic leadership - only such persons can apply or be nominated.

Present and former Vice-Chancellors, Directors/Heads of Institutions of Higher learning/ Research Institutions and eminent scholarly persons are invited to nominate. The Search Committee reserves the right to consider a person of eminence outside the list of such applications/nominations. The search committee shall recommend a panel of three suitable persons for the consideration of the State Government for being appointed as the Vice-Chancellor. The State Government shall appoint one of the persons included in the panel referred to above.

As per section 13(1) of the IITE Act, the Vice-Chancellor shall hold office for a term of five years from the date he enters upon his/her office or till attaining the age of sixty-five years, whichever is earlier, and shall not be eligible for re-appointment. The powers and functions of the Vice-Chancellor are mentioned in section 14 of the IITE Act.

The Application/Nomination should be submitted in hard copy by speed post/registered AD/ courier in a sealed envelope marked "Application/Nomination for Vice-Chancellor Position" addressed to The Chairman, Search Committee for appointment of Vice-Chancellor, C/o. The Registrar, Indian Institute of Teacher Education, Ramkrushna Paramhans Vidya Sankul, Near KH-5, KH Road, Sector - 15, Gandhinagar - 382016 (Gujarat), and same should also be emailed to searchcommittee@iite.ac.in on or before 26/03/2024. The candidates shall apply in the prescribed format available on the IITE website.

Date : 23/02/2024

Registrar

PUNYASHLOK AHILYADEVI HOLKAR SOLAPUR UNIVERSITY, SOLAPUR

[Under Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2016]
Phone No.0217-2744770 Email-registrar@sus.ac.in

Applications are invited from the eligible candidates in the prescribed format for the following posts on the establishment of the Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Solapur University, Solapur.

Advt. No. : PAHSUS/Estt/2024/182

Sr. No.	Name of the Post	No. of Post	Category
01	Finance and Accounts Officer	01	Unreserved
02	Director, Innovation, Incubation and Linkages	01	Unreserved
03	Director of Sports and Physical Education	01	Unreserved

Duly completed, application in prescribed form, along with all enclosures, shall be sent to the Registrar, Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Solapur University, Solapur – 413 255 so as to reach on or before 10/04/2024 (Up to 05.30 p.m.).

Further details can be downloaded from the University website sus.ac.in and <http://su.digitaluniversity.ac> link of Employment Opportunities. The same is hosted on Govt. of Maharashtra website www.maharashtra.gov.in

Sd/-
(Yogini Ghare)
Registrar

Date : 06/03/2024

MAHARASHTRA NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY AURANGABAD

(University established under Act No. VI of 2014 by State Legislature of Maharashtra)

Date: 07/03/2024

ADVERTISEMENT FOR THE POST OF VICE-CHANCELLOR

The Maharashtra National Law University, Aurangabad invites applications from eligible candidates for the post of Vice-Chancellor.

The Vice-Chancellor shall be a distinguished academic with a minimum of ten (10) years of experience as:

1. a Professor of Law in a college on a post approved by a University **OR**
2. a Professor of Law in a University **OR**
3. in an equivalent position in a reputed research and / or academic administrative organization

The candidate must demonstrate academic and administrative leadership and possess the highest levels of professional competence, personal integrity, and institutional commitment.

Key Terms and Conditions:

- a) s(he) shall be a full-time salaried officer of the university;
- b) s(he) shall hold office for a term of five (5) years or until the attainment of the age of sixty-five (65) years, whichever is early, and shall be eligible for renewal for a further term of five years or till s(he) attains the age of sixty-five years, whichever is early, by a resolution to that effect by the Executive Council of the University; and
- c) s(he) shall not be more than sixty-five (65) years of age as on the last date of submission of the application.
- d) s(he) shall demonstrate excellence in teaching and research at the national and international levels.

Interested candidates may submit their application in the prescribed format, CV and Vision Statement for MNLU-Aurangabad (not exceeding 1500 words) by email at searchcommittee2024@mnlua.ac.in and by post duly super-scribing the envelope 'Application for the post of Vice-Chancellor', to 'The Convenor, Search Committee, Maharashtra National Law University, Aurangabad, Paithan Road, Kanchanwadi, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra-431011' on or before April 06, 2024.

For the detailed notification, visit the official website of the University: www.mnlua.ac.in.

Sd/-
Convenor, Search Committee
Maharashtra National Law University, Aurangabad.

NIRMALA MEMORIAL FOUNDATION COLLEGE OF COMMERCE AND SCIENCE D.S. Road, Asha Nagar, Thakur Complex, Kandivali (E), Mumbai – 400 101

MINORITY

APPLICATIONS ARE INVITED FOR THE FOLLOWING POSTS FROM THE ACADEMIC YEAR 2023-24:

UN-AIDED

Sr. No.	Cadre	Subject	Total No. of Posts	Category
1.	Assistant Professor	Accountancy	02	02 – OPEN
2	Assistant Professor	Commerce	02	02 – OPEN
3.	Sports Director	Physical Education	01	01 - OPEN
4.	Librarian	--	01	01 – OPEN

The above posts are open to all, however candidates from any category can apply for the post.

Reservation for women will be as per University Circular No.BCC/16/74/1998 dated 10th March 1998. 4% reservation shall be for the persons with disability as per University Circular No. Special Cell/ICC/2019-20/05 dated 05th July, 2019.

Candidates having knowledge of Marathi will be preferred.

“Qualification, Pay Scales and other requirement are as prescribed by the UGC Notification dated 18th July, 2018, Government of Maharashtra Resolution No. Misc-2018/C.R.56/18/UNI-1, dated 8th March, 2019 and University Circular No. TAAS/ (CT)/ICD/2018-19/1241, dated 26th March, 2019 and revised from time to time.”

The Government Resolution & Circular are available on the website mu.ac.in.

Applicants who are already employed must send their application through proper channel. Applicants are required to account for breaks, if any in their academic career.

Application with full details should reach the SECRETARY, NIRMALA MEMORIAL FOUNDATION COLLEGE OF COMMERCE & SCIENCE, D.S. Road, Asha Nagar, Thakur Complex, Kandivali (E), Mumbai - 400 101 within 15 days from the date of publication of this advertisement. This is University approved advertisement.

Sd/-
SECRETARY

MADHEPUR TEACHERS' TRAINING COLLEGE

Madhepur, Madhubani(Bihar)-847408

Contact No.9334049113,9801832516

E-Mailid: mttcollege@gmail.com • Website [www: mttcollege.org.in](http://www.mttcollege.org.in)

(A Unit of Sheikh Abdul Jalil Foundation, Darbhanga)

Recognized by ERC, NCTE, Bhubaneswar, 2 (f) & 12B Granted by UGC

(Permanently Affiliated to LNMU, Darbhanga & BSEB, Patna)

Employment Notice for B.Ed. and D.El.Ed. Programs

Applications are invited from eligible candidates, as per NCTE Norms for the post of Asst. Professor (B.Ed.) and (D.El.Ed.), Lecturer, Librarian and Accountant. Application Along with Resume, Documents of Academic and Professional Qualification, Photographs, Adhar card, PAN Card, Voter I.D and Experience Certificate, if any, latest by 30/04/2024 for the post of faculty in Perspective in **Edu., Pedagogy Subjects (Science, Maths, Hindi, English, Urdu) Visual and Performing Arts, Health & Physical Education.** For detail Information kindly go through Advertisement published on 13/12/2021& 18/07/2022 in **Quami Tanzeem**, on 18/12/2021 on 18-07-22 in **Prabhat Khabar in Education News, a weekly Journal vol. 60. No. 48, Nov. 28 to December 4,2022** or visit Website. [www : mttcollege.org.in](http://www.mttcollege.org.in) (Note; if NET/Ph.D. qualified candidates are not available, preference will be given to Experience Holders)

Sd/-
Secretary

Nath Shikshan Prasarak Mandal Pingli GOKULNATH ART'S COMMERCE & SCIENCE SENIOR COLLEGE Pingli Tq. Dist. Parbhani

WANTED

Applications are invited from the eligible candidates for the following posts in Gokulnath Art's, Commerce & Science Senior College Pingli Tq. Dist. Parbhani (Permanent Non Grant) run by Nath Shikshan Prasarak Mandal, Pingli Tq. Dist- Parbhani. The applications duly complete in all respects should reach on the following address **within 15 days**. The candidates of reserved category should submit one copy of application to the Dy. Registrar, Special Cell, S.R.T.M.U, Nanded **within 15 days** from the Advt. Published.

Name of the Post	Subject	Sanctioned Posts	Total Posts	Category
Principal	-	1	1	OPEN-1
Associate Professor	English	2	18	OPEN - 07 SC - 02 ST - 01 VJA - 01 NTB - 01 NTC - 01 OBC - 03 EWS - 02
	Marathi	2		
	Hindi	2		
	History	1		
	Political Science	1		
	Economics	1		
	Commerce	2		
	Chemistry	1		
	Mathematics	1		
	Botany	1		
	Zoology	1		
Microbiology	1			
Director of Physical Education	-	1		
Librarian	-	1		

Note: 1) Details as per SRTMU Nanded on website

2) Qualification as per UGC & SRTMU Nanded rules

Contact : The President, Nath Shikshan Prasarak Mandal Pingli Sanchalit, Gokulnath Art's Commerce & Science Senior College Pingli Tq. Dist. Parbhani. M. No. 9420883512.

Kasegaon Education Society's
Rajarambapu Institute of Technology, Rajaramnagar
 Islampur, Tal. Walwa, Dist. Sangli 415414 (Maharashtra)
(An Empowered Autonomous Institute, Affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur)
(Permanently Non Granted)

WANTED

Applications are invited from eligible candidates for the following posts:

B. Tech.				
Sr. No.	Name of Posts	Vacant Posts	Open Posts	Reserved Posts
A. Professor				
1	Civil Engineering	01 FT	01	---
2	Computer Engineering	01 FT	01	---
3	Computer Science & Information Technology	01 FT	01	---
4	Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering	01 FT	01	---
5	Electrical Engineering	01 FT	01	---
6	Mechanical Engineering	02 FT	01	01 SC
B. Associate Professor				
1	Civil Engineering	02 FT	---	01 SC, 01 VJA
2	Computer Engineering	05 FT	02	01 SC, 01 VJA, 01 OBC
3	Computer Science & Information Technology	03 FT	01	01 SC, 01 VJA
4	Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering	02 FT	---	01 SC, 01 VJA
5	Electrical Engineering	03 FT	01	01 SC, 01 VJA
6	Mechanical Engineering	01 FT	---	01 SC
7	Mathematics	01 FT	01	---
C. Assistant Professor				
1	Computer Engineering	10 FT	02	01 SC, 01 ST, 01 NTB, 01 NTC, 03 OBC, 01 EWS
2	Computer Science & Information Technology	03 FT	---	01 ST, 01 VJA, 01 EWS
3	Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering	04 FT	---	01 SC, 01 NTC, 01 OBC, 01 EWS
4	Electrical Engineering	03 FT	---	01 SC, 01 ST, 01 EWS
5	Mechanical Engineering	05 FT	---	01 ST, 01 NTD, 01 OBC, 02 EWS
6	Mathematics	04 FT	02	01 SC, 01 VJA
7	Chemistry	01 FT	01	---
8	Physics	02 FT	01	01 SC
9	Professional Communication	03 FT	01	01 SC, 01 VJA
D	Director of Physical Education	01 FT	01	---
B. Tech (New Courses, Increase in Intake) & MBA – IEV (New Course)				
A. Professor				
1	Computer Engineering	01 FT	01	---
2	Mechatronics Engineering	01 FT	01	---
B. Associate Professor				
1	Mechatronics Engineering	03 FT	01	01 SC, 01 VJA
2	Computer Science & Engineering (Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning)	01 FT	01	---

(contd. on pg. 46)

(contd. from pg. 45)

3	MBA (Innovation Entrepreneurship and Venture Development)	01 FT	01	---
C.	Assistant Professor			
1	Computer Engineering	02 FT	01	01 SC
2	Mechatronics Engineering	08 FT	03	01 SC, 01 ST, 01 VJA, 01 OBC, 01 EWS
3	Computer Science & Engineering (Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning)	04 FT	02	01 SC, 01 VJA
4	Robotics & Automation	01 FT	01	---
5	MBA (Innovation Entrepreneurship and Venture Development)	03 FT	01	01 SC, 01 VJA
6	Physics	01 FT	01	---
7	Mathematics	02 FT	01	01 SC
8	Chemistry	01 FT	01	---

Note:- For detailed information about posts, qualifications and other terms and conditions please visit University website: www.unishivaji.ac.in Apply with prescribed format available on the Institute website www.ritindia.edu.

Place : Rajaramnagar (Islampur)

Date : 23/02/2024

Director
Rajarambapu Institute of Technology,
Rajaramnagar, Islampur

Balaghat Shikshan Sanstha, Naldurg's,

Arts, Science and Commerce College, Naldurg

Tq. Tuljapur, Dist. Dharashiv

(Affiliated to Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar)

WANTED

Applications are invited from the eligible candidates for the following vacancy in our college as specified below:

Sr. No.	Name of the Post	No. of Post	Category
01	PRINCIPAL	01	OPEN

Educational Qualification:

1. A Master's Degree with at least 55% marks (or equivalent grade in a point scale wherever grading system is followed) by a recognized University.
2. A Ph.D. Degree in concerned/allied / relevant discipline(s) in the institution concerned with evidence of published work and research guidance.
3. Associate Professor/Professor with a total experience of 15 years of teaching/research/administration in Universities/ College and other institutions of higher education.
4. A minimum score as stipulated in the Academic Performance Indicator (API) based on Performance Based Appraisal System (PBAS) for Professors / Principal as developed by Govt. of India Gazette 18-24 Sept., 2010, Maharashtra State Govt. notification dated 15th Feb., 2011 & Educational qualifications recommended by the U.G.C. and State Government from time to time.

Salary & Allowances: Pay Scale as per the U.G.C., Maharashtra State Government & Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar.

Note: 1. The post of Principal shall be a tenure post. The term of appointment of the college Principal shall be for five years with eligibility for re-appointment for one more term only after a similar selection committee process.

2. No T.A. & D.A. will be paid for the candidates attending the interview.

3. Eligible Candidates those who are already in services, should submit their application through proper channel.

4. The post is transferable in the colleges under Balaghat Shikshan Sanstha, Naldurg.

5. The recruitment procedure initiated by this advertisement is subject to the outcome of the writ petition No. 12051/2015 pending before the High Court.

6. The Eligible Candidates should submit their applications along with attested photo copies of all educational certificates required for the post, other relevant documents & related proof of API score should be attached with the application form on the address mentioned below:

'The Secretary, Balaghat Shikshan Sanstha, Naldurg's--Arts, Science and Commerce College, Naldurg, Tq. Tuljapur, Dist. Dharashiv (Maharashtra) - 413601.'

7. Application should be submitted by **22nd March, 2024** to the above address. Applications received after **22nd March, 2024** will not be considered. The Institute / College will not be responsible for postal delay, if any.

Shri Ulhas Borgaonkar
Secretary,
Balaghat Shikshan Sanstha, Naldurg

Shri Madhukarrao Chavan
President,
Balaghat Shikshan Sanstha, Naldurg

Shri Vaishnav Vidyapeeth Vishwavidyalaya

Indore-Ujjain State Highway, INDORE-453111.

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ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

The candidates directly seeking admission in the Ph.D. program should be possessing postgraduate degree or equivalent in the relevant subject from any recognized University in India or abroad with at least 55 Percent marks or 5.5/10 CGPA in aggregate and for SC/ST candidates the minimum marks of 50 percent or 5/10 CGPA in aggregate. The merit list for admission will be based on the score obtained by a candidate in SVET-2024 and personal interaction. As per Govt. Guidelines those candidates who do not have the required minimum percentage (55% marks) in their Master's Degree, should have completed an AIU recognized/AICTE approved postgraduate diploma in the subject/area/discipline in which he/she seeks to do Ph.D. and has secured at least 55% marks in such diploma. However, admissions will be made only on his/her merit position based on the score obtained in SVET-2024 & personal interaction.

How to Apply:

Interested candidates should register for SVET-2024 by applying in the prescribed application form available at <http://www.svvv.edu.in> and then to SVET link <https://online.cbexams.com/SVET/svetreg2024/Login.aspx> The prescribed fees for the Registration is ₹ 1000/- for all candidates. Options for payments of fees are given on the University website.

SCAN & APPLY

Deadline to register for SVET-2024 by filling the online form along with the prescribed fee for Ph.D. program is 24th April 2024, till 5:00 PM.

Date for SVET Online Exam: **28th April, 2024**

Test Centre: @ your home on your Device (Desktop/Laptop) with WebCam.

City Office: Shri Vaishnav Vidya Parisar, 177 Jawahar Marg, INDORE-452002

Campus: Ujjain Road, Indore-453111 **Mob:** 9303700163, 9303700164, 9303700165, 9303700166, 9303700167, 9303700168 **Toll Free No:** 18002339111, **Help Line No:** 18001029191, **Email:** admission@svvv.edu.in

Note: The Candidates who are exempted from Entrance Test as per UGC Guidelines need not to appear in SVET-2024. However, they have to appear for the personal interaction and must get registered as per procedure given above.

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